

ANIMA

Aviation Noise Impact Management
through Novel Approaches

D3.10 Studies on Virtual and Auralisation tools

Project Information	
PROJECT ID	769627
PROJECT FULL TITLE	Aviation Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches
PROJECT ACRONYM	ANIMA
FUNDING SCHEME	RIA – Research and Innovation action
START DATE OF THE PROJECT	01.10.2017
DURATION	48 months
CALL IDENTIFIER	H2020-MG-2017-SingleStage-INEA
PROJECT WEBSITE	www.anima-project.eu
Deliverable Information	
DELIVERABLE N° AND TITLE	D3.10 Studies on Virtual and Auralization tools
TYPE OF DELIVERABLE¹	Report
DISSEMINATION LEVEL²	PU (2-year embargo starting end of October 2021)
BENEFICIARY NUMBER AND NAME	20 – UCP - CYU
AUTHORS	Romain Dedieu (CYU) – Catherine Lavandier (CYU)
CONTRIBUTORS	Roalt Aalmoes (NLR) – Henk Lania (NLR) – Isabelle Boulet (Airbus) – Ingrid Legriffon (ONERA)
WORK PACKAGE N°	3
WORK PACKAGE LEADER	Roalt Aalmoes
WP LEADER VALIDATION DATE	08/11/2021
COORDINATOR VALIDATION DATE	08/11/2021
COORDINATOR SIGNATURE	

¹ Use one of the following codes: R=Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC=Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER=Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Use one of the following codes: PU=Public, fully open, e.g. web
CO=Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement
CI=Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Version follow-up		
Update	Name	Version
September 17 th , 2021	Catherine Lavandier and Romain Dedieu (CYU)	V0
October 11 th , 2021	Roalt Aalmoes (NLR)	V1
October 11 th , 2021	Ingrid Legriffon (ONERA)	V2
October 14 th , 2021	Isabelle Boulet (AIRBUS)	V3
November 2 nd , 2021	Catherine Lavandier and Romain Dedieu (CYU)	V4

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	7
Description and objective	7
2. Laboratory study	8
2.1. Context	8
2.2. Method and material.....	9
2.2.1. Selection of audio-visual stimuli	9
2.2.2. The non-varying parameters: trajectory, listener position, and background noise.....	14
2.2.3. Participants	16
2.2.4. Subjective assessments	19
2.2.5. Procedure.....	20
2.2.6. Material	21
2.3. Results.....	23
2.3.1. Method	23
2.3.2. Analysis of all questions - Correlations	24
2.3.3. Overall pleasantness	25
2.3.4. Audio-Visual Realism.....	39
2.3.5. Sound Pleasantness	42
2.3.6. Loudness.....	45
2.3.7. Final overall evaluation	48
2.4. Conclusion of the laboratory experiment	51
3. In situ study	52
3.1. Context	52
3.2. Method and Material	55
3.2.1. Aircraft audio-visual model.....	55
3.2.2. Landscape	57
3.2.3. Trajectory	58
3.2.4. Background noise	60
3.2.5. Participants	61
3.2.6. Procedure.....	62
3.2.7. Material	63

3.2.8.	Questionnaire and Persona.....	63
3.3.	Results.....	64
3.3.1.	COVID impact	64
3.3.2.	Relation with air traffic	64
3.3.3.	Classical communication method feedbacks	66
3.3.4.	Assessing the change with immersive virtual simulations.....	67
3.4.	Conclusion of the in situ study.....	70
Conclusion and recommendations:		72
Bibliography		73
Appendix A		74
	Calibration method.....	74
Appendix B		76
	A reduced version of the Noise Sensitivity Questionnaire (NoiSeQ), named the R-NoiSeQ	76
Appendix C		78
	The EUROHIS-QOL 8-Item index according to Da Rocha [8].....	78
Appendix D		80
	Final questionnaire	80
Appendix E		82
	Stimuli Order	82
Appendix F		86
	ANOVA tables for global pleasantness.....	86
Appendix G		88
	Presentation for the situ study at the workshop in the city of Beauchamp.....	88
Appendix H		97
	Communication letter to Beauchamp residents	97
Appendix I		98
	Preliminary questionnaire for the focus groups.....	98
Appendix J		101
	Persona summary from CIGALE project	101
Appendix K		107
	Ethical comity validation (ad-hoc).....	107

Appendix L	108
Information document – Laboratory experiment.....	108
Appendix M	114
Information document – In situ experiment	114

1. Introduction

Description and objective

Auralization and visualization tools have the potential to provide credible communication and engagement with people around airports and to allow for the integration of audible and visual aircraft noise-related information in interactive land-use planning. This might lead to more effective communication and engagement which can help to reduce levels of annoyance. In order to enhance the trust from residents towards authorities and enable planners to include future airport scenarios in land-use planning, the validity of the tool, such as congruence between vision and audition, has to be respected. When this is achieved, stakeholders can then imagine themselves in real situations. Another advantage is the controlled, simulated environment: events can be played in the same way, under the same circumstances for each participant. Other influences, such as weather, time of day, or external events can be controlled or ignored. It also allows the presentation of events in different places known to the people such as their home, work place and locations for leisure-time and recreation.

In order to evaluate the usefulness of such a tool, two experiments have been carried out.

The first experiment aimed to assess the validity of the Virtual Community Noise Simulator (VCNS) developed by the Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre (NLR) [1]. This simulator is able to present an audio-visual experience of a simulated aircraft flyover. This first experiment was conducted in a controlled laboratory context, where 60 participants were invited to test the tool. A statistical analysis was then possible to better understand the influence of the visual setting and of the sound of aircraft on the quality of the simulated environment. This first part was necessary to verify that the tool itself gives enough confidence on the restitution. Parameters such as “familiarity” or “congruence between vision and audition” have been studied with perceptual tests performed by CYU. The experimental set-up was elaborated together with ONERA, AIRBUS and NLR. When the validity of the VCNS tool had been established, a second experiment was carried out to evaluate the use of such a virtual tool within the framework of an information and communication campaign.

The second experiment tried to evaluate the advantage of the use of the VCNS compared to a classical communication campaign about a real change in approach procedure. The experiment was organized in Beauchamp (Val d’Oise, France, 25km far from Roissy Charles de Gaulle) where a continuous descent approach should be applied to all flyovers in 2023. Residents of Beauchamp were invited to participate in workshops, where this future change was presented with classical maps and figures. The VCNS was used, at the end of the workshops, and the participants were invited to “virtually experience” the previous presented change. Two workshops gathered all together 10 participants. No statistical analysis had been possible but mind maps were drawn in order to summarize the discussions and the advantages of the virtual tool compared to the classical approach.

2. Laboratory study

2.1. Context

Amongst novel approaches that could enhance the communication between local planners and communities around airports, some virtual reality tools (auralization and visualization) can be used by residents to give them better understanding of the impact of future airport scenarios in land-use planning, as the virtual reality creates a higher immersion for the user (See Figure 1).

The Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre (NLR) has developed a Virtual Community Noise Simulator (VCNS) to support airport communities and other stakeholders who want to experience aircraft noise in their own environment by using the latest virtual reality technologies with 360 degrees' video and 3D audio experience. Such tools have proven to be convincing in previous research and demonstrations [1]–[3].

A laboratory perceptual experiment has been carried out in order to assess the relevance of such a tool for simulating flyover in regards to realism, and to study influence of the landscape (visual) associated to the background (audio) and to the vision of the aircraft (here the size and the architecture of the source) on the sound evaluation of the flyover.

Figure 1: Virtual Community Noise Simulator (VCNS) illustration.

The design of the experiment should allow to answer the following research questions:

- Does the quality of the landscape have an influence on the perceived quality of the environment when aircraft fly?
- Do visual characteristics of the aircraft (size, novelty, hidden source by clouds) have an influence on the perceived environment?
- Do acoustic characteristics have influence on the perceived environment?

2.2. Method and material

2.2.1. Selection of audio-visual stimuli

In order to evaluate the VCNS, 24 audiovisual stimuli have been designed (See Figure 2). The goal of the listening test being the influence of the visual impact on noise perception, the three sounds will be mixed with the visual data.

Figure 2: Laboratory study - Design of experiment.

The audio-visual scenes were defined according to three perceptual dimensions:

- The landscape;
- The aircraft sound synthesis (auralizations);
- The aircraft visual model.

2.2.1.1. The landscapes

The virtual environments consist in 2 urban landscapes. Half the scenes take place in an urban district, and the other half take place in a park (See Figure 3). They have been recorded in Paris suburb (see in Section 2.2.6 A p.21). Videos durations are 200 s, and 160 s long respectively for the urban district, and the park.

Figure 3 : Landscape screenshots used for the laboratory study. Urban space recorded in a Sarcelles district (on left) and Green space recorded in a Saint-Brice sous Forêt park, in France (on right).

2.2.1.2. The aircraft visual models

The visuals of three distinct aircraft are used for the experiment. These three aircraft are the Airbus single aisle family (noted A320 Family), a wide body aircraft, noted A380, and a revolutionary design called the "BOLT" (Blended wing body with Optimized Low-noise Technologies, see Figure 3), anticipated for 2050 operations.

a) *BOLT, a blended wing body (BWB) anticipated for 2050 operation, equipped with generic Ultra High Bypass Ratio (UHBR) engines mounted on pylons on the top of the centerbody (© University RomaTre, 2018)*

b) *Airbus A320-family*

c) *Airbus A380*

d) *Hidden aircraft due to cloudy sky*

Figure 4: Four visuals consisting in three aircraft visual models (a) the BOLT aircraft, (b) the Airbus A320 family, (c) the Airbus A380, and (d) one visual for which the aircraft cannot be seen due to the presence of clouds.

BOLT has been conceived and designed in [European Union's Horizon 2020 research project ARTEM](#) (Aircraft noise Reduction Technologies and related Environmental iMPact - G.A. N°769 350). These 3D models are superimposed on the virtual environment in the simulator, creating an augmented view of a virtual flyover of these aircraft. A separate background mask is used in the simulation software to

ensure the aircraft are not visible behind obstructing trees or buildings in the virtual environment.

The aircraft models have different MTOW (Maximum Take-Off Weight) capabilities. Design MTOW for BOLT is 230 metric tons, whereas A320 is around 70 mt, and A380 is around 500 mt.

2.2.1.3. The aircraft sound syntheses

The notion of auralization is defined here as a series of software composed of noise prediction tools and sound synthesis tools.

For the experiment, all aircraft approaches have been synthesized in accordance with a one-segment certification trajectory defined in Section 2.2.2. The BOLT sound synthesis was designed by ONERA prediction tool [4] whereas A320neo, and A380 flyover were synthesized by Airbus prediction tool.

The ONERA in-house series of software CARMEN / FLAURA, and the Airbus in-house ROOTS software combined with the commercial tool GENEPASS are based on different modelling hypotheses, and methodologies. An auralization comparison has been conducted during the ANIMA project and results are presented in Deliverable D4.4 [5]. The BOLT sound has been synthesized including fan noise, landing gear noise and flap noise. It is important to notice that the simulations of the BWB and the Airbus type aircraft have not been carried out by the same series of software.

The main outcomes of these sound syntheses are the mono audio signals corresponding to the three aircraft flyovers. The wave files have been synchronized to ensure that the max dB SPL is reached at the time 30 s for each sound synthesis.

In the approach phase, the turbofan is at quiet low engine power operating conditions. The fan tip rotation speed is therefore subsonic and no buzz-saw noise (BSN) appears. The broadband contribution of both the fan, and the aeroacoustic noise due to air friction (airframe noise, in the form of flap and landing gear noise) are thus the main contributors to the overall aircraft sound syntheses. Regarding the BOLT sound synthesis, even if BOLT is supposed to be equipped with UHBR engines, since the noise model for such engines does not exist yet, classic lower bypass ratio engines were used to predict their contribution in the noise synthesis.

Both the SPL and the loudness evolutions over time are presented in Figure 5 below. The Airbus A380 (in green) is over the entire flyover duration the loudest in terms of SPL (in dB). It's also almost all the time the loudest in terms of sones even if the differences are reduced.

The BOLT is louder than the A320neo up to $t \approx 30s$ corresponding to the time when the max SPL is reached. After this time, A320neo becomes louder than BOLT.

In the table in Figure 5, some global acoustic indicators are presented (L_{eq} , N, and max SPL). A380 gets the highest values for both indicators. The smallest max SPL (in dB) is obtained by the A320. In terms of equivalent sound levels, both the BOLT and the A320neo are almost equal (65.5 Vs 65.4 dB respectively).

Figure 5: Plot of SPLs (on left), and loudness (on right) over time and Table of global acoustic indicators (Leq, Loudness, max SPL) for the three sound syntheses (BOLT, A320neo, A380). The time when the max SPL values are reached for all sound syntheses is shown in dotted black line.

The resulting global acoustic indicators show that A380 is louder and gets the highest max SPL (See **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**).

	BOLT	A320neo	A380
Leq [dB]	65.5	65.4	70.9
Loudness [sone]	13.6	12.5	15.4
Loudness [phon]	77.6	76.5	79.5
Max SPL (@30sec) [dB]	71.3	72.1	76.1

Table 1: Global acoustic indicators (Leq, Loudness, max SPL) for the three sound auralizations (BOLT, A320neo, and A380 flyover at approach).

Other psycho-acoustic indicators are presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** For all the equivalent sound indicators, A380 sound synthesis is the loudest (EPNL, Leq, SEL, loudness). A320neo and BOLT sound syntheses have quite close equivalent sound indicators (Leq, SEL, and loudness) although BOLT's EPNL is 1 dB higher.

	BOLT	A320neo	A380
EPNL [EPNdB]	79.5	78.5	82.3
N₅ [sone]	20.6	19.4	23.1
N₁₀ [sone]	19.6	18.4	22.0
L₅ [phon]	83.7	82.8	85.3
L₁₀ [phon]	82.9	82.0	84.6
L_{A,10} [dB(A)]	65.4	65.0	67.8
Max Loudness [sone]	21.9	21.9	25.1
Max Loudness [phon]	84.5	84.5	86.5
Max SPL (time step = 0.5s) [dB(A)]	66.4	66.8	68.7
Max SPL (time step = 0.5s) [dB(C)]	71.2	72.0	75.9
L_{A,eq} [dB(A)]	60.0	59.6	62.4
L_{C,eq} [dB(C)]	65.3	65.3	70.6
SEL [dB]	84.1	84.0	89.5
Spectral centroid [Hz]	388	357	229
Sharpness [acum]	1.09	0.93	0.87
Roughness [vacil]	0.03	0.03	0.04
Average Tonality Aures [tu]	0.07	0.05	0.05

Table 2: Acoustic and psycho-acoustic indicators for BOLT, A320neo, and A380 sound syntheses.

A380's spectral centroid is the lowest (229 Hz), and BOLT's one the highest (388 Hz).

Figure 6: Specific Fluctuation strengths of the three flyover simulations (BOLT, A320neo, and A380).

Roughness, and fluctuation strength indicators are low whatever the aircraft sound synthesis. Indeed, atmospheric turbulence effects have not been accounted for in the syntheses and are among the main causes of fluctuations in amplitude or frequency.

Finally, tonality is low too whatever the sound synthesis because of the operating conditions (standard 1 segment approach at low airspeed without BPF tones, nor buzz saw noise).

2.2.2. The non-varying parameters: trajectory, listener position, and background noise

In order to study the interaction of the audio and the aircraft visual only, some parameters must remain constant:

2.2.2.1. The background noise

The sample has been selected from the measurement campaign carried out in Paris suburb (a park in city of Beauchamp, 85 Avenue Anatole France) in September 2019 by NLR. The recording session is described in Section 2.2.6. This sound sample will be used for both the urban and the park locations.

The sound sample consists in sounds of nature with the presence of birds chirping, wind, and sounds of moving leaves in trees. A scooter passing by at distance is also noticed.

The sample is a 1st order ambisonic recording. It's synchronized with the 360° videos, and has been calibrated at 45 dB(A) in terms of equivalent sound pressure level according to the calibration method described in Section 2.2.6 B p.21.

The sound analysis is carried out based on the mix of the four channels of the ambisonic recording resulting in one mono signal analysis.

The spectrogram is presented in Figure 7. Most of the acoustic energy is below 2 kHz. Some brief slight peaks at higher frequencies (5 kHz, 7 kHz, etc.) are however found corresponding to the birds chirping. The SPL evolution over time is then detailed in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Background noise Spectrogram (color bar unit is in dB)

The evolution is quite smooth and not varying much. One peak is noticed at time = 30 s corresponding to a scooter passing by at distance.

Figure 8: Background noise sound pressure level evolution (in dB(A)) over time (blue line). Equivalent Sound Pressure Level $L_{A,eq}$ equal to 45 dB(A) is shown in dotted black line.

This background noise is always part of the sound environment during the experiment and sound emergence depends on the floor level. Thus, emergence indicators are presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** in considering the total mix (Background noise + Flyover sound synthesis). In order

to compute the emergence indicators, the background noise with its four channels (1st order ambisonic recording) were mixed all together to get one mono channel. This resulting mono channel was eventually mixed with each of the three sound syntheses prior computing the emergence parameters.

	BOLT	A320neo	A380
$L_{10} - L_{90}$ [dB(A)]	17.4	18.2	17.9
$N_{10} - N_{90}$ [sone]	14.0	12.9	15.1

Table 3: Emergence indicators for the three flyover

2.2.2.2. The aircraft trajectory, airspeed, and slope

The aircraft trajectory (See Figure 9) is defined with respect to a one-segment trajectory, with a constant slope and a constant calibrated airspeed. In order to have the same trajectory for both aircraft, CAS (Calibrated Air Speed) has to be the same and, for this reason, corresponds to the average of A320neo and A380. BOLT trajectory follows the same path.

2.2.2.3. The listener position

The listener is located at $x=10.5\text{km}$, $y=380\text{m}$, $z=1.2\text{m}$ to the runway threshold. However, the listener is free to move his head and rotate on a chair so that the entire 360° scenery is accessible by sight.

Figure 9: A320neo, A380 and BOLT trajectories (blue line) (Altitude vs. distance to runway) and x listener position (dotted black line).

2.2.3. Participants

60 listeners participated in the listening test. A hearing test was conducted for every participant and the audiogram release showed that two listeners had too significant hearing losses in order to remain in the corpus. The decision was taken based on the audiometric classification of hearing impairment [6].

Among the 58 remaining participants (57% female / 43% Male), 29 participants are aged between 18-29 years old, and the other half is aged between 30-50 years old (See Figure 10 on top left). They have been selected so that there are as many young individuals (18-29 y-o) as older listeners (30-50 y-o) in order to assess

whether the age has an influence in the subjective assessment of the VR technology.

Other personal pieces of information were collected for the experiment:

- Zip code
- Questionnaire assessing the noise sensitivity developed by Griefahn [7] (See Appendix B p.76) ; Results are presented in Figure 10 (bottom right)
- Questionnaire assessing the Quality of Life (QoL) developed by Da Rocha [8] (See Appendix C p.78). Mean results are presented in Figure 10 (bottom left).

The descriptive variables are presented in Figure 10. The age distribution, the gender repartition, the sensitivity to noise, and the quality of life distributions are displayed.

	Age category	
	18-29	30-60
Sensitivity to noise		
Non-Sensitive (<=6.3/10)	14	12
Sensitive(>6.3/10)	15	17

Figure 10: Panel of participants - distributions according to the age, the gender, the quality of life [8], and the noise sensitivity [7]. Mean values according to the age category are presented in dotted colored vertical lines.

2.2.4. Subjective assessments

A. Audio-visual stimuli evaluation in the virtual world

During the experiment, participants were asked to fill a questionnaire assessing each of the 24 audio-visual stimuli. The experiment lasted less than an hour and a two minutes break was recommended to all participants after completing the twelve first stimuli.

Table 4: Audio-visual stimuli's subjective assessment. Screenshots of the questions as they appear in the virtual world (in French) and the questionnaire translation in English

English translation	Screenshot in the Virtual World
<p>OVERALL, does this situation seem more or less:</p> <p>Unpleasant Unbearable Valider</p>	
<p>Does the ASSOCIATION of the sound with the visual seem more or less:</p> <p>Unrealistic Non credible Valider</p>	
<p>Does the SOUND of this aircraft seem more or less:</p> <p>Unpleasant Unbearable Valider</p>	

In order to facilitate the listening test operability, the questionnaire showed up in the virtual world. It consists in four questions, two relative to the overall audio-visual environment, and 2 focused on the aircraft flyover sound. Table 4 presents the questionnaire as it appears in the virtual world. For each stimulus, the questionnaire shows up 10 s after the aircraft sound is maximal in terms of dB SPL.

Participants used the joystick on the touch controller in order to move the white cursor on the 101 points scale with semantic differential [-50, +50]. At any time, they can replay the audiovisual stimulus to refine their assessment.

B. Final questionnaire

The final questionnaire is arranged in several parts.

The first part aims to assess the simulator overall efficiency in restituting the reality (See Appendix D). The second part aims to assess the listener noise sensitivity. It's a French translation of the R-NoiSeQ [7] and it consists in 12 questions. The questionnaire is detailed in Appendix B p.76.

The third part evaluates the participant's self-evaluation regarding his/her quality of life. The questionnaire is detailed in Appendix C, p.78 and is a French translation of the EUROHIS-QOL 8-Item index [8].

The fourth part collects personal information (see Table 21 in Appendix D).

2.2.5. Procedure

The protocol had been reinforced due to the corona virus outbreak. Listeners were first informed of the nature of the experiment: "Study of a new method to engage the airport community about airplane noise: the virtual reality". The onboarding document is then read and signed by the subject (See Appendix L p.108).

The audio impairment evaluation is then introduced, and the audiogram test is conducted. Whatever the result of the audiogram release, they all kept on with the VR experiment.

After having installed the VR equipment in making sure the visual is clear, and that the background sound is clearly perceptible, the experiment can start. First, a training session consisting in two audiovisual stimuli is carried out allowing the listeners to become familiar with the VR equipment and to the experiment (assessing the audio-visual environment by replying to 4 questions in using the

joystick of the touch controller). At any time, participants are allowed to replay the audio-visual stimulus as long as the questionnaire is not totally filled. When they validated the fourth and last question, a new stimulus was presented.

The first measured part consists in evaluating all 12 first audiovisual stimuli in the same 360° landscape. One half of the participants started with the green landscape and the other half with the urban district (See Figure 3). After completing the first session, the participants took off the headset and had a 5-min break.

The second part took then place in the other landscape with the second series of audiovisual stimuli assessment.

As soon as they finished the audio-visual test, they filled the final questionnaire described in Section 2.2.4 p.20.

They were given a gratification of 30 euros at the end of the experiment.

The order of stimuli was designed to ensure that:

- The randomization of the stimuli order was controlled to ensure a rather regular distribution;
- Half the participants started in Landscape 1 (park) and continued in Landscape 2 (urban district) and the other half had the reversed order (Landscape 2 → Landscape 1);
- The aircraft visual cannot be the same two times in a row;
- The aircraft sound cannot be the same two times in a row.

The stimuli order for each participant is provided in Appendix E p.82.

2.2.6. Material

A. 360 degrees' videos

The 360 degrees' videos were captured in the area of Paris Charles de Gaulle airport thanks to a camera rig on which was installed 10 GoPro cameras (See Figure 12). Video stitching software was used to combine the individual videos into a single spherical video.

The recordings took place in September 2019 by NLR in cooperation with UCP. The description of the procedure is described in Deliverable D4.6 of ANIMA project [9]. Two landscapes recorded during this measurement campaign were selected for the laboratory study:

1. Allée Jean de la Bruyère, 95200 Sarcelles
2. Rue Jean Jaurès, 95350 Saint Brice sous Forêt

B. Background noise

The background noise has been recorded with Zoom H3-VR recorder³. This device is a first

Figure 11: The 360 degrees camera rig for 10 GoPro cameras.

³ More info about the Zoom H3-VR recorder [here](#)

order ambisonic audio recorder. The ambisonic background noise is then spatially rendered thanks to an ambisonic decoder. Recording has been carried out in a Beauchamp's park in Paris suburb. A Rion Sound Level Meter was also used at the same time to measure the sound level of the environment, but this recording was not used during the reproduction in the simulator.

C. VR equipment

The Virtual Reality equipment consists in the Oculus Rift device running on a laptop DELL Precision 7730 with a graphic card NVIDIA Quadro P5250.

Along with the headset (see Figure 13), two touch controllers are provided. For the experiment, only the left touch controller has been used.

At very few times, some lagging has occurred during the session due to overheating. When that occurred, a small break time was proposed to the participants. As soon as the equipment had cooled down, the experiment resumed.

Oculus provides small headphones attached to the rift but they have not been used for the experiment. The headset Sennheiser HD650 plugged on a soundcard RME Fireface UC. The headset sensitivity response has been determined prior the experiment. The calibration results are presented in Appendix A.

D. Calibration method

The objective of the calibration is to ensure that the SPL listened through the headset by the participants correspond to the targeted SPL for each sound stimulus (Background noise, and the 3 aircraft sound syntheses).

Regarding the aircraft sound syntheses, the calibration procedure has been carried out based on the maximal SPLs in dB(A) (integration step = 0.5s). The calibration method ensured that the corresponding max sound levels are met in adjusting the amplification gains for each sound stimulus. To do so, we estimated what output AC voltage should be measured at the soundcard output. The expected AC voltage for each sound stimulus is defined thanks to the linear interpolation equation of the headset HD650 calibration data (See Figure 47). The equation has been defined thanks to the linear interpolation of the following calibration curve: $\log(V_{AC\ RMS}) = f(SPL\ [dB(A)])$. Based on this calibration curve, the targeted voltages are calculated (see details in Appendix A, Table 17 p.74).

Regarding the background noise, since it's not changing too much in level over the sample duration (max-min < 4dB), the calibration has been carried out in taking the overall $L_{A,eq} = 45\ dB(A)$ for target. For an equivalent background sound level equal to 45 dB(A), the adequate output voltage should be equal to 1.6 mV. It was unfortunately not possible to measure such low voltage output with the equipment available in the lab. An alternative has been preferred using a calibrated pink noise reference. To adjust the calibration process, the pink noise was played on the setup, and the output voltage has been measured (much higher than 1.6 mV). From this voltage measurement, the correspondent SPL dB(A) value has been

Figure 12: Picture of the Oculus Rift device (headset + touch controllers).

calculated thanks to the headset calibration curve. The pink noise would then be used as reference to equalize the background noise at the targeted value ($L_{A,eq} = 45 \text{ dB}(A)$).

E. Audiometer

The audiogram has been conducted on the device Interacoustics AD226. This audiometer allows to evaluate the audio impairment from 100 Hz to 5000 Hz.

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Method

For each of the 4 questions proposed after each audiovisual stimulus, an Analysis of Variance is first carried out.

The experimental design described in Section 2.2 makes it possible to carry out a repeated measure ANOVA. Such analyses need to respect some assumptions such as distribution normality.

When such assumptions are not met, non-parametric statistical analyses are then preferred: Friedman-test for repeated measures design ([10], [11]).

Following the parametric or non-parametric analysis, when some factors (dependent variables) show an influence on the observed variable, a post-hoc analysis is carried out.

Finally, when different people viewpoints are observed, additional analyses are carried out to better understand the clusters. Principal component and hierarchical clustering (HCPC) are the two main statistical methods used to highlight, and characterize the main viewpoints.

In order to synthesize the results, the hypotheses verifications are not detailed in this report.

2.3.2. Analysis of all questions - Correlations The questionnaire displayed after each audio-visual situation consists in four questions (see Section 2.2.4). Correlation calculations between pairs of distributions show that some of the questions are related (each distribution consisting of all the responses for a given question, see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Correlations between pairs of distributions according to the question asked (audiovisual realism, overall pleasantness, sound pleasantness, and perceived loudness)

The sound pleasantness is highly correlated to the perceived loudness (correlation = -0.86). The louder the aircraft, the least pleasant the sound. The overall pleasantness is also highly correlated with the sound pleasantness (correlation = 0.85) showing that participants had difficulties in distinguishing between the two questions. In contrast, the audiovisual realism is not correlated with any other question. The absence of correlation demonstrates that this realism does not depend of the experienced situation. We will see in Section 2.3.4 that the audiovisual realism is quite good whatever the situation.

2.3.3. Overall pleasantness

A. General results

The first question is: OVERALL, does this situation seem more or less (translated from French):

Unpleasant	Pleasant
Unbearable	Bearable
-50	+50

As described in Section 2.3.1, in first approach, a linear analysis of variance (ANOVA) is proposed with a mixed model and following a repeated measures design.

The dependent variable is the quantitative variable with all participants overall pleasantness ratings according to the audiovisual stimulus.

One first model studied three independent variables:

1. The qualitative variable describing the aircraft sound syntheses (3 levels)
2. The qualitative variable describing the aircraft visual model (4 levels: 3 aircraft visual models + 1 with a cloudy sky);
3. The qualitative variable describing the landscape where the assessment was carried out (2 levels).

Anova results are presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable..**

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
A.C.Sound	1, 72.12	352.23	37.89 ***	.02	<.0001
A.C.Visual	2.60, 148.07	329.00	9.23 ***	.01	<.0001
Landscape	1, 57	604.35	0.80	.0007	.38
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.92, 280.32	196.05	0.13	.0002	.98
A.C.Sound:Landscape	1.78, 101.36	146.06	0.03	<.0001	.95
A.C.Visual:Landscape	2.52, 143.44	166.18	0.22	.0001	.85
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual:Landscape	5.20, 296.45	196.68	1.28	.002	.27

Table 5: ANOVA summary for the evaluation of the landscape, the aircraft visual and the aircraft sound auralizations influences on the overall pleasantness ratings (df: degrees of freedom, MSE: Mean Square of the Error, ges: generalized eta square). Greenhouse-Geisser corrections are applied due to lack of sphericity.

Both the aircraft sound, and visual have an influence on the overall pleasantness evaluations even if the effect size is low (ges are 2%, and 1%, respectively). The landscape does not have an influence on the ratings according to the ANOVA results. Finally, there is no audio-visual interaction.

Post hoc analysis (.i.e. analysis made without any prior assumption on relations between data groups) is then carried out with the pairwise comparisons for the two factors having a significant influence on the ratings, which are the aircraft visual models, and the sound syntheses (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Post hoc pairwise comparison for the overall pleasantness estimated means according to the aircraft visual model and the aircraft sound synthesis (-50: Unpleasant ; +50: Pleasant). Individual observations are plotted in circles shades of grey and estimated mean values are depicted in black points. Error bars show the "within-subjects standard errors/confidence intervals" following Cousineau's approach [12].

The influence of the visual emerges mostly because of the stimuli with an overcast sky. With the presence of clouds, the overall pleasantness is significantly reduced. The influence of the aircraft sound model is mainly due to the Airbus A380 sound synthesis which tends to deteriorate the perceived overall pleasantness. Overall pleasantness is worsened with the airbus A380 sound and corresponds to the differences of the aircraft flyover acoustic properties (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** p.**Erreur ! Signet non défini.**). Indeed, A380 aircraft sound is louder (3 EPNdB louder than the A320neo) and has a lower spectral centroid (equal to 229 Hz, the lowest).

B. Focus on the flyover repetition effect coupled with the landscape influence

The landscape does not seem to influence the overall pleasantness assessments (according to the results of ANOVA in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**). This result was unexpected, the park being more attractive than the urban district. A few oral comments during the experiment might help understand this result.

Some participants (Subjects S1, S26, S43) explained at the end of the experiment that hearing and seeing aircraft in a relaxing green park is more annoying than being disturbed by it in the urban district where they expected such disturbance. These participants would rate the overall pleasantness of the virtual environment lower in the green park rather than in the urban district. In other words, being disturbed by aircraft flyover in a place where relaxation is expected and wished (here being the park) is more annoying than in a place where the subject is more tolerant because he was not keen to rest anyway because the context does not fit.

Subject S26 said⁴:

« *Being in the urban square makes plane passages more bearable because it is more consistent with the environment.* »

Subject S43 said⁵:

« *In a park, whether at a low noise level or not, it is unpleasant to hear the airplane while in town it is less problematic. When we go to a park, it's to put all kinds of urban noise aside.* »

There is a second hypothesis that might explain this unexpected result: the fatigue effect. There is a tendency showing that participants tend to lower their ratings with the repetition of flyover (See Anova results in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**). In adding an independent variable in the model coding for the test part, whether the stimulus was assessed during the first part (first 12 stimuli after the training session) or the second part (last 12 stimuli after the break).

It must be reminded that half the participants carried out the first part of the test in the green park and finished the test in the urban district, whereas the other half performed the test in the reverse order.

ANOVA results (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) show that there is an influence of the test part on the overall pleasantness ratings, with a slight decrease in overall pleasantness in the

	Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
1	A.C.Sound	1.27, 72.12	352.23	37.89 ***	.02	<.0001
2	A.C.Visual	2.60, 148.07	329.00	9.23 ***	.01	<.0001
3	testPart	1, 57	573.21	3.94 +	.003	.05
4	A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.92, 280.32	196.05	0.13	.0002	.98
5	A.C.Sound:testPart	1.78, 101.42	146.00	0.03	<.0001	.96
6	A.C.Visual:testPart	2.57, 146.65	154.14	3.34 *	.002	.03
7	A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual:testPart	5.17, 294.69	199.45	0.82	.001	.54

Table 6: ANOVA summary for the evaluation of the test part, the aircraft visual and the aircraft sound syntheses influences on the overall pleasantness ratings (df: degrees of freedom, MSE: Mean Square of the Error, ges: generalized eta square). Greenhouse-Geisser corrections were applied due to lack of sphericity.

Some free comments in the final questionnaire confirm that result:

Subject S26 said⁶:

⁴ translated from French: « Le fait d'être dans la cité rend les passages d'avions plus supportables parce que plus en cohérence avec l'environnement. »

⁵ translated from French: « Dans un parc que ça soit à un niveau faible ou non, c'est désagréable d'entendre l'avion alors qu'en ville c'est moins problématique. Quand on va dans un parc c'est pour mettre toutes sortes de bruits urbains de côté. »

⁶ : translated from French: « Au début, je tolérais bien les passages d'avions, mais à force des répétitions, cela m'irrite de plus en plus et ça devient plus difficilement supportable »

« At first, I tolerated the passage of planes well, but with repetitions, it irritates me more and more and it becomes more difficult to bear. »

Subject S56 said⁷:

« I pity the people who live there... At the beginning, it's bearable but with the repetition it becomes annoying because of the frequency of flyover. »

Figure 15: Repetition effect: Post hoc pairwise comparison showing the decrease in overall pleasantness (-50: Unpleasant ; +50: Pleasant) during the second part compared to the first part of the experiment according to the aircraft sound synthesis. Error bars show the "within-subjects standard errors/confidence intervals" following Cousineau's approach [12]. Estimated mean values are depicted in black points and individual ratings are in circles shades of grey.

So, since there is an order effect due to the repetition of aircraft flyover, a cross analysis between the landscape environment and the order in which they have been assessed is needed. Results of the analysis of variance are presented in Table 7. The influence of the repetition of flyover is confirmed as well as the absence of influence of the landscape type (Park or urban district).

Table 7: ANOVA summary for the evaluation of the landscape, and the landscape influences on the overall pleasantness ratings (df: degrees of freedom, MSE: Mean Square of the Error, ges: generalized eta square).

	df	MSE	F	p.value
Landscape	1	480.7	0.920	0.3376
testPart	1	2255.7	4.318	0.0379 *
Landscape:testPart	1	667.6	1.278	0.2585

Based on the analysis of variance, the landscape type does not have a significant influence on the ratings. Another type of analysis (PCA) is developed in Section 2.3.3 D p.30 and provides an additional interpretation of the landscape influence. First, the analysis of variance continues with the study of the influence of personal variables on the overall pleasantness evaluations.

⁷ : translated from French: « Je plains les personnes qui habitent là au début c'est supportable mais avec la répétition ça devient pénible en raison de la fréquence des passages.»

C. Personal variables

In order to evaluate the effect of personal variables on the overall pleasantness rating, a mixed plan Anova is carried out for each of the following variables taken separately (QoL variable, Sensitivity to noise, Age, Gender, Aircraft familiarity, Virtual reality familiarity, and video games familiarity).

The design is not always well balanced because the selection of participants has only been carried out based on the age category. Anova tables are presented in Appendix F p.86.

Both the noise sensitivity and the age influence the overall pleasantness (p-values < 0.05, and <0.10 respectively). In average, young individuals' ratings are higher (situations assessed more pleasant). Similarly, the ratings of the individuals sensitive to noise are higher too (see Figure 16). Why did younger participants find the situations more pleasant in overall than older participants?

A first interpretation might come from their sensitivity to noise. In our panel, older individuals are slightly more sensitive to noise than the younger ones [13] (mean sensitivity is equal to 6.4 for the 30-50 y-o group and is equal to 5.8 for the 18-30 y-o group).

Another assumption is proposed. The youngest might assess more pleasant the situations if they are more used to the VR technology. But the results show that they are not significantly more familiar to the VR technology than older ones (chi-squared test gives p-value = 0.41 when comparing the VR familiarity and the Age variables, see Figure 31 p.50).

In contrast, both the gender and the quality of life, and the three familiarity assessments don't have any influence on the perception (See Appendix p.86).

Figure 16: Age and noise sensitivity effect on the overall pleasantness: Post hoc pairwise comparison showing the overall pleasantness (-50: Unpleasant ; +50: Pleasant) according to the aircraft sound model and and 2 personal variable a)the age category, and b) the noise sensitivity. Error bars show the "within-subjects standard errors/confidence intervals" following Cousineau's approach [12]. Estimated mean values are depicted in black points and individual ratings are in circles shades of grey.

D. A widely spread dispersion

Results showed significant dispersion of ratings among the participants. In order to highlight the main viewpoints, a Principle Component Analysis (PCA) is carried out followed by a HCPC (hierarchical clustering using the Euclidean distance measure and following Ward's method).

$$\begin{matrix}
 & \begin{matrix} 1 & & k & & K=24 \end{matrix} & \begin{matrix} \text{Mean} \\ \text{mean}(x_{11}:x_{1K}) \\ \\ \text{mean}(x_{i1}:x_{iK}) \\ \\ \text{mean}(x_{I1}:x_{IK}) \end{matrix} \\
 \begin{matrix} 1 \\ \\ i \\ \\ I=58 \end{matrix} & \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & \dots & x_{1k} & \dots & x_{1K} \\ \vdots & \ddots & & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & x_{ik} & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{I1} & \dots & x_{Ik} & \dots & x_{IK} \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} \text{mean}(x_{11}:x_{1K}) \\ \\ \text{mean}(x_{i1}:x_{iK}) \\ \\ \text{mean}(x_{I1}:x_{IK}) \end{pmatrix}
 \end{matrix}$$

Figure 17: Dataset arrangement used for the PCA and definition of the additional Mean variable.

The variables for the PCA are each of the 24 audio-visual stimuli, and every observation is a participant's rating (matrix of 58 rows x 24 columns, see Figure 17). So, each participant is characterized by 24 dimensions. Some of these

dimensions could be correlated to each other which would mean that this original matrix could be reduced with fewer dimensions (less than 24). PCA tries to find the minimum number of dimensions which explains the variability of the participants' ratings. The first component which is extracted from the PCA corresponds to the dimension where the participants are the most spread out (maximum of variability between observations). The second dimension is then extracted in finding the orthogonal component compared to the first one which maximizes the variability (etc. for the further dimensions).

The inertia explained for each dimension is presented in Figure 18. The first dimension explains more than 60% of the total variability in the dataset. There is a significant gap between the first and all the other dimensions since the second principal dimension represents only 6.4% of the total variability. Based on these explained variances only the first main dimension should be selected and analyzed in details, but the second dimension has been nevertheless kept because it explains differences between people point of views.

Figure 18: Global pleasantness: Inertia explained for each dimension of the PCA.

The first outcome of the PCA is presented in a diagram in where the variables are the audio-visual stimuli according to their correlations with the two main dimensions. The variable labelling is described in Table 8.

Table 8: Nomenclature designated the audiovisual stimuli in the PCA correlation diagram

Denomination	Landscape	Aircraft model	sound	Aircraft model	visual
ParkSBoltVBolt	Park	BOLT		BOLT	
ParkSA320VBolt		A320neo		BOLT	
ParkSA380VBolt		A380		BOLT	
ParkSBoltVA320		BOLT		A320neo	
ParkSA320VA320		A320neo		A320neo	
ParkSA380VA320		A380		A320neo	
ParkSBoltVA380		BOLT		A380	
ParkSA320VA380		A320neo		A380	
ParkSA380VA380		A380		A380	

ParkSBoltVClouds	Urban square	BOLT	Clouds (no A/C)
ParkSA320VClouds		A320neo	Clouds (no A/C)
ParkSA380VClouds		A380	Clouds (no A/C)
UrbanSBoltVBolt		BOLT	BOLT
UrbanSA320VBolt		A320neo	BOLT
UrbanSA380VBolt		A380	BOLT
UrbanSBoltVA320		BOLT	A320neo
UrbanSA320VA320		A320neo	A320neo
UrbanSA380VA320		A380	A320neo
UrbanSBoltVA380		BOLT	A380
UrbanSA320VA380		A320neo	A380
UrbanSA380VA380		A380	A380
UrbanSBoltVClouds		BOLT	Clouds (no A/C)
UrbanSA320VClouds		A320neo	Clouds (no A/C)
UrbanSA380VClouds		A380	Clouds (no A/C)

In order to evaluate the quality of the variable projections in the PCA plan, the indicator \cos^2 is used as defined in Equation 1:

$$\cos^2 = \cos(\varphi_{x_1k})^2 + \cos(\varphi_{x_2k})^2 \quad (1)$$

With a \cos^2 the closest to 1, the better the quality of the variable representation. Results of the PCA are first presented on a correlation diagram where the audiovisual stimuli are represented by arrows (See Figure 19). Three additional variables are represented for information and have never been used to construct the principle components (sensitivity to noise, quality of life, mean variable over all stimuli ratings as described in Figure 17).

The quality of representation is good for all variables and even very good for most since the \cos^2 is always greater than 0.55 (min \cos^2 for UrbanSA380VBOLT) and reach up to 0.85 with the variable ParkSA320VA320.

Figure 19: Correlation diagram from PCA showing a representation of the audiovisual stimuli according to their correlations with the two main dimensions of variability in the dataset. Informative supplementary variables are added in blue. Variables are represented as arrows and the color is defined based on the indicator \cos^2 as defined in equation 1.

This diagram shows that all variables are positively correlated to the first dimension of the PCA meaning that it's a consensual dimension.

Regarding the second dimension along the y axis, there is a divide because of the landscape influence on the evaluations. 10/12 variables corresponding to the audio-visual stimuli evaluated in the park are positively correlated to the second dimension, and reciprocally 10/12 variables corresponding to situations evaluated in urban square are negatively correlated to this second dimension. We can interpret this dimension as the difference in perception toward the landscape.

The differences in perception can be interpreted in displaying the participants coordinates on the correlation diagram (see Figure 20).

Figure 20: PCA results for the overall pleasantness ratings – Bi-plot showing both the variables (the stimuli) and the participants coordinates (in colored circles + ID labels) on the two main dimensions of the PCA. Variables are represented as arrows and the color is defined based on the indicator \cos^2 as defined in equation 1.

First regarding the first factor, it shows that the participants are widely spread over the entire axis. The participant S12 for example is opposed with the participant S51 on this dimension (See Figure 21).

Figure 21: Overall pleasantness ratings according to the audio-visual stimuli for the two best contributors to dimension 1 of the PCA: Subjects S12, and S51

It shows that Subject S12 found pleasant all stimuli whereas Subject S51 evaluated all stimuli (except one) unpleasant.

In order to illustrate the interpretation of the second factor, ratings of two participants are presented in Figure 22. Participants with a quite high and positive coordinate on dimension 2 (Example with S42) tend to assess more pleasant the audiovisual stimuli in the park whereas the participants with negative and quite high (in absolute) coordinate on this same second dimension tend to prefer the audiovisual stimuli in the urban square (Example with S21 on Figure 22).

Figure 22: Overall pleasantness ratings according to the audio-visual stimuli for two opposed contributors on dimension 2 of the PCA: Subjects S21, and S42

So even if the analysis of variance does not show any influence of the landscape, it's partly because two viewpoints are opposed on this topic with one group preferring the park (S3, S5, S21, S43) and another preferring the urban district (S4, S11, S42, S50). There isn't additional descriptive variable that highlight commonalities for each group.

Next, the additional quantitative variables (Mean, Sensitivity, QoI) are studied to see whether they might be correlated to the PCA factor. First the mean variable describes the overall mean rating per participant over all stimuli (see Figure 17). The correlation of this mean variable with the first dimension is 0.999. So, the first factor of the PCA is the mean vector. Participants who found unpleasant the stimuli in mean have a negative coordinate on this first dimension, those who have a neutral opinion (in mean) of the audiovisual stimuli pleasantness have a coordinate close to zero on this first dimension and those who found pleasant in overall the stimuli (in mean) have a high coordinate value on this same axis.

Moreover, the second additional variable describing the sensitivity to noise of each participant has a correlation greater than 0.3 in absolute (see Figure 19) indicating a light relationship, still highly significant, between the mean evaluation of overall pleasantness and the sensitivity to noise.

Finally, a HCPC (hierarchical clustering) is carried out and the resulting dendrogram is presented in Figure 23.

Based on the analysis of the dendrogram, the choice to keep 3 clusters looks reasonable given the distance distributions. With 3 clusters, the groups are quite well balanced consisting in respectively 19, 21, and 18 participants. For information, these three clusters are shown with ellipse shapes in Figure 20 with the same color representation.

Based on this clustering, some additional statistical tests are carried out in order to characterize the three groups based on socio-demographic data.

In order to assess whether a quantitative variable characterizes one of the three groups, the "v-test" is calculated as defined in Section 3.3 of the document describing the FactoMineR library [14].

It results that subjects in cluster 1 (the displeased group) are significantly more sensitive to noise (7.5/10 compared to the overall mean among participants equal to 6.1/10).

In contrast, participants in cluster 2 are significantly less sensitive to noise (5.3 in the cluster compared to 6.1 in the panel).

For the additional categorical variables (Age, Sensitivity, Video games familiarity, Virtual reality familiarity, Aircraft familiarity (Q15 - Q17 in Table 20)), Chi-squared tests are carried out. Results are presented in Table 9.

The sensitivity categorical variable has a p-value lower than 0.05 and the age categorical variable (2 groups 18-29, and 30-50) has a p-value lower than 0.1 suggesting a tendency of relation. Subjects in the first cluster are significantly older than in the whole panel. 41% of all 30-50 y-o participants are part of this cluster 1, completed with 27% of the 18-30 y-o group.

Subjects in the third cluster have a reversed repartition in age, with 48% of all 18-30 y-o participants and 21% of all 30-50 y-o subjects. Cluster 2 is more evenly mixed with 37% of all 30-50 y-o participants, and 24% of all 18-30 y-o participants.

Regarding the participants assessments of their familiarity to play Videogames (Figure 31c p.50), their familiarity to observe aircraft flyover near their dwelling (Figure 31a), and their familiarity toward the virtual reality technology (Figure 31b), chi-squared tests show that these three variables are not describing the 3 clusters since the p-values are higher than 0.10. No relation has been found (see Table 9).

Figure 23: Overall pleasantness assessment Dendrogram resulting of the Hierarchical clustering (cluster 1 in blue, cluster 2 in yellow, cluster 3 in grey)

Table 9: Pearson's Chi-squared test for characterizing the 3 main clusters based on the additional categorical variables

	Pearson's χ^2 test	df	p-value	
Age	4.89	2	0.087	+
Sensitivity	11.5	2	0.0032	**
Vr Familiarity	1.87	4	0.75	
Videogames Familiarity	2.26	4	0.69	
Aircraft Familiarity	5.37	4	0.25	

To summarize, the first dimension of the PCA helps understand where the variability in the dataset does come from. The main source of variability is due to 3 main viewpoints:

Cluster 1: The group rather sensitive to noise, with a higher proportion of 30-50 y-o individuals, was displeased in overall by the audiovisual stimuli;

Cluster 2: The group rather non-sensitive to noise, whatever the age, has rated the overall pleasantness in the middle of the range;

Cluster 3: The group with a higher proportion of 18-30 y-o individuals, was pleased in overall by the audio-visual stimuli.

As a result, mean evaluations of overall pleasantness per cluster are presented in Figure 24: Overall pleasantness per HCPC cluster for each of the 24 audio-visual stimuli. Figure 24 and confirm the analysis of the first factor.

Figure 24: Overall pleasantness per HCPC cluster for each of the 24 audio-visual stimuli.

2.3.4. Audio-Visual Realism

The second question is: Does the ASSOCIATION of the sound with the visual seem more or less: (translated from French):

Unrealistic	Realistic
Non-credible	Credible
Incoherent	Coherent
-50	+50

As an introduction, the distributions are presented in the shape of boxplot in Figure 25.

First outcome, the evaluations are in average always positive. Mean ratings are greater than 15 on the scale [-50 ... +50]. Overall, the audio-visual realism is evaluated quite good whatever the scenario.

In looking at the boxplot shapes for each distribution, the non-normality appears clearly. ANOVA cannot be carried out for such non-normal distributions.

Figure 25: Audiovisual realism according to the aircraft sound synthesis and the visual model. Distributions are presented in boxplot shape. Mean value for each combination of aircraft sound and visual model are in white circle, and overall mean value according to the aircraft visual model are in black diamond (-50 = Unrealistic ; +50 = Realistic)

A first observation on this Figure shows that the congruence between vision and sound perception (V.BOLT/S.BOLT; V.A380/S.A380 and V.A320/S.A320) does not increase the realism of the stimuli. So, there was no incongruency in our audio-visual stimuli which could have reduced the perceive realism of the tool.

Non-parametric study is then preferred and Friedman test followed by the pairwise comparison of Nemenyi are carried out. Results of Friedman test are presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** and Nemenyi post-hoc evaluation is detailed in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**

Friedman rank sum test			
	Friedman χ^2 test	Df	p-value
Aircraft Visual	19.73	3	1.932e-04 ***
Aircraft Sound	2.920	2	0.2323
Landscape	0.1579	1	0.6911

Table 10: Audio-visual realism – Influence of the aircraft visual, sound, and of the Landscape. Results of the Friedman rank sum test.

The aircraft visual is the only variable having a significant influence on the ratings. Nemenyi tests presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** show in association with the analysis of the boxplot distributions presented in Figure 25 that the audio-visual realism is significantly improved when the aircraft visual model is the airbus A320neo.

Nemenyi Pairwise comparison on the aircraft model visual			
	BOLT	A380	A320neo
A380	0.9731		
A320neo	0.00274**	0.01200*	
Clouds	0.9662	0.80536	0.00044***

Table 11: Audio-Visual Realism - Nemenyi pairwise comparison showing the influence of the aircraft visual.

A few participants comments might help understand this result. Feedbacks regarding the presence of clouds in the sky show that overcast sky was not very realistic according to some participants:

Subject S49 said:

“I noticed a drop in realism with the overcast sky because we should still have seen the plane under the clouds. Therefore, it was more disturbing”.⁸

Subject S35 said:

« The pixelation and realism of clouds needs to be improved in my opinion ». ⁹

Subject S60 said:

« The presence of clouds undermines the realism. I realized that there were clouds later in the test because the situation had the same brightness with or without clouds, and it was not consistent»¹⁰

⁸ « J’ai remarqué une baisse de réalisme avec le ciel couvert parce qu'on aurait quand même dû voir l'avion sous les nuages. Du coup c'était plus dérangeant. » Subject S49

⁹ « La pixellisation et le réalisme des nuages est à améliorer selon moi. » Subject S35

¹⁰ « La présence de nuages nuit au réalisme. Je me suis rendu compte que c'était des nuages plus tard dans le test avec la même luminosité ce qui n'était pas cohérent ». Subject S60

Regarding the BOLT visual model, since this airplane does not exist nowadays, participants noticed a drop in realism. For example, participant S24: "The park and the square are very realistic. On the other hand, the situations where the plane is a spatial ship were not at all realistic for 2020."¹¹

Regarding the airbus A380 visual model, we assume that some participants might not be very familiar with such a big aircraft and felt it was not realistic. For example, participant S19 said: "The biggest plane seemed to me very or even too close to the floor, almost in the tree"¹².

Finally, the absence of influence of both the landscape and the aircraft sound synthesis in the ANOVA results (see **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**) suggests that these two factors contributes to the overall good evaluation of audiovisual realism for both landscapes, and for all the three syntheses indifferently.

¹¹ « Le parc et la place sont très réalistes. En revanche, les situations où l'avion est une soucoupe volante n'étaient pas du tout réalistes pour 2020 ». Subject 24

¹² « Le plus gros avion me paraissait très voire trop proche, limite dans l'arbre ». Subject S19

2.3.5. Sound Pleasantness

A. General results

The third question is: Does the SOUND of this aircraft seem more or less (translated from French):

Unpleasant Unbearable	Pleasant Bearable
-50	+50

Anova results (see in Table 12) confirm the influence of both the aircraft sound and visual with the addition of the interaction between the three dependent variables. Results are quite similar to those presented in Section 2.3.3 A, regarding the question about overall pleasantness. However, for the aircraft pleasantness, the effect size of the aircraft sound is a bit higher ($ges=0.03$ Vs 0.02 in overall) and the visual influence is lower ($ges=0.005$ Vs 0.01 in overall). Whereas the sound was twice more important than picture for the overall pleasantness, the sound is six times more important than picture for sound pleasantness, which is very coherent with the questions, and which shows that participants did make the difference between them.

Table 12: ANOVA summary for the evaluation of the landscape, the aircraft visual and the aircraft sound auralizations influences on the sound pleasantness ratings (df: degrees of freedom, MSE: Mean Square of the Error, ges: generalized eta square). Greenhouse-Geisser corrections are applied due to lack of sphericity

Effect	df	MSE	F		ges	p.value
A.C.Sound	1.64, 93.23	296.84	41.32	***	.028	<.001
A.C.Visual	2.58, 146.83	294.94	4.45	**	.005	.008
Landscape	1, 57	755.44	0.03		<.001	.854
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	5.08, 289.32	159.83	0.96		.001	.444
A.C.Sound:Landscape	1.97, 112.38	113.62	0.98		<.001	.378
A.C.Visual:Landscape	2.80, 159.66	120.21	1.18		<.001	.319
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual:Landscape	4.83, 275.34	219.61	2.62	*	.004	.026

Post hoc analysis is then carried out and presented in Figure 26.

Airbus A380 sound synthesis gets the lowest ratings in mean. A380 sound auralization is less pleasant than A320neo, and BOLT sound syntheses according to the participants.

Regarding the visual influence on the sound pleasantness evaluation, post hoc analysis shows that the presence of clouds tends to lower the evaluations of sound pleasantness.

A.C. Visual Bolt A380 A320 Clouds

Figure 26: Post hoc pairwise comparison for the sound pleasantness estimated means according to the aircraft visual model and the aircraft sound synthesis (-50: Unpleasant ; +50: Pleasant). Individual observations are plotted in circles shades of grey and estimated means are in black circles.

B. Correspondences between mean perceived sound pleasantness and acoustic indicators

This section aims to compare the perceptive evaluation of sound pleasantness with the objective acoustic and psycho acoustic indicators describing the aircraft sound syntheses. For this experiment, only 3 sound stimuli of aircraft flyover have been assessed in various visual situations. With only 3 datapoints, correlation calculation between subjective, and objective assessments seem irrelevant. Nevertheless, a graphical analysis is preferred allowing to compare these two types of metrics (See Figure 27).

Figure 27: Correspondences between mean perceived sound pleasantness and acoustic indicators
 x-axis scale is: -50: Unpleasant ; +50: Pleasant.

The max SPL in dB(A) as well as the spectral centroid are the acoustic indicators that best follow the sound pleasantness.

2.3.6. Loudness

A. General results

The fourth question is: Does the SOUND of this aircraft seem more or less (translated from French):

Loud	Low
50	-50

Anova results confirm the influence of both the aircraft sound and visual. In addition, there are tendencies of interaction of the three dependent variables influences altogether as well as the interaction between the aircraft sound and the aircraft visual.

The results are quite similar to what was found for both the question regarding the overall pleasantness, and the sound pleasantness. The effect sizes are equal between the perceived loudness, and the sound pleasantness variable ($ges_{ACsound} = 0.028$ and $ges_{ACvisual} = 0.005$).

Table 13: ANOVA summary for the evaluation of the landscape, the aircraft visual and the aircraft sound syntheses influences on the loudness ratings (df: degrees of freedom, MSE: Mean Square of the Error, ges: generalized eta square). Greenhouse-Geisser corrections are applied due to lack of sphericity

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
A.C.Sound	1.71, 97.65	262.99	40.44 ***	.028	<.001
A.C.Visual	2.47, 140.83	260.24	4.49 **	.005	.008
Landscape	1, 57	559.60	0.30	<.001	.588
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	5.25, 298.98	158.66	1.89 +	.002	.092
A.C.Sound:Landscape	1.91, 108.75	122.34	0.07	<.001	.927
A.C.Visual:Landscape	2.86, 162.84	107.12	0.32	<.001	.801
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual:Landscape	5.15, 293.67	161.88	2.16 +	.003	.057

Again, the influence of the aircraft sound comes from the evaluation of the aircraft A380 which is perceived louder than the other two.

The influence of the visual is mostly due to the audiovisual stimuli where the aircraft could not be seen because of the presence of clouds. The sound tends to be perceived louder when the noise source is not visible (the p-value of the interaction between vision and audition is under 0.1). For example, the sound of the BOLT aircraft is perceived louder when it's hidden behind the clouds. This effect is more sensitive in the urban landscape (See Figure 28).

The aircraft size has not influenced the perception of loudness. For a given sound stimulus, the differences in loudness are not significantly different when the A320neo is seen (narrow body), compared to when the aircraft visual model is the A380 (wide-body).

Figure 28: Post hoc pairwise comparison for the sound pleasantness estimated means according to the aircraft visual model, the aircraft sound synthesis, and the landscape (-50: Low; +50: Loud). Individual observations are plotted in colored points and estimated means are displayed in black circles.

B. Correspondences between mean perceived loudness and acoustic indicators

This section aims to compare the perceived loudness evaluations with the objective acoustic indicators. Figure 29 compare the mean perceived loudness and the acoustic indicators describing the aircraft sound stimuli. The louder (in terms of EPNL, N10, max SPL, max Loudness, L10) is also perceived louder.

The indicator L10-L90 in dB(A) shows that all flyover have similar emergences values (max difference < 1 dB(A)). Since they are close, the mean perceived loudness does not follow the same order.

Finally, the perceived loudness follows the same order than the spectral centroid. The higher the spectral centroid, the lower the flyover is perceived.

The max SPL in dB(A) as well as the spectral centroid are the acoustic indicators that best follow the perceived loudness.

It can be noticed that the lowest aircraft in loudness is the BOLT although its EPNL is 1 dB higher than the A320neo one. This difference is likely due to its high frequency content which could come from the auralization strategy.

Figure 29: Correspondences between mean perceived loudness and acoustic indicators. The abscise scale is: [-50=Low; +50=Loud]

2.3.7. Final overall evaluation

The final questionnaire allows to assess the virtual simulator VCNS. A few relevant perceptual dimensions have been assessed:

Immersion (Q7, Q9, Q11 in

- Table 20 p.80)

Control (Q13 in

- Table 20)

Audio and visual quality (Q3, Q4 in

- Table 20)

Overall audio and visual realism (Q1, Q2 in

- Table 20)

VR sickness (headache, vertigo...) (Q8, Q10, and Q12 in

- Table 20)

Proprioception (Q5, Q6 in

- Table 20)

When several questions are asked regarding a given perceptual dimension, they are aggregated altogether. Results are presented in Figure 30. Participants assessed that the experiment was very immersive since 91% of all ratings show an agreement with the three following statements:

- *"I felt surrounded by the environment."*
- *"I paid more attention to the environment than to my thoughts (personal concerns, daydreams, etc.)."*
- *"I felt like I was physically present in the environment."*

The simulations have been assessed very realistic for a majority of participants and 18% of them found it extremely realistic. The audiovisual quality is good according to a majority of participants and both the remote controller and the head movement fidelity in the virtual world have been assessed good for 32% and excellent for 56%. Even if there were few means of control in the virtual environment (the avatar was static in translation), they have been positively assessed.

Finally, even if a large majority of participants have not mentioned any sensation of dizziness due to the VR equipment, a few subjects suffered from headache or they felt a bit sick (10% of them).

Last, the results of the 3 final questions are presented in Figure 31 describing the participants familiarity with regard to:

1. the presence of aircraft flyover near their dwelling;
2. the virtual reality, and with regard;
3. playing videogames.

a) Immersion

b) Audiovisual realism

c) Audiovisual quality

d) Cues for Proprioception

e) Control

f) Fatigue

Figure 30: Final questionnaire – Overall evaluation of the VCNS simulator

In the panel, 41 % are not used to seeing airplanes flyover near their dwelling, and 48% are on the contrary more used to it leading to a rather largely spread distribution of responses (Figure 31a). A majority of participants are not used to play videogames and even 71% of them are not familiar of the VR experience.

a) Aircraft familiarity

b) Videogames familiarity

a) Virtual Reality familiarity

Figure 31 : Subjective evaluation of the participants' familiarity toward a) the presence of aircraft near their dwelling, b) the video games, and c) the virtual reality technology according to the age category. Percentage labels corresponds to the proportion of participants in the panel who answered the indicated response.

2.4. Conclusion of the laboratory experiment

A laboratory study has been designed in order to assess the validity of a virtual reality tool, to help engage airport community. Some criteria have been evaluated such as congruence, realism, perception of immersion in the virtual environment, etc.

3 perceptual dimensions have been crossed resulting to 24 audio-visual stimuli designed based on the mix of:

- 3 aircraft sound syntheses;
- 4 flyover visuals;
- 2 landscapes.

60 participants assessed each of the audiovisual stimuli individually.

The analysis of variance demonstrates the influence of both the aircraft visual, and the aircraft sound on the perceived aircraft loudness, and the aircraft sound pleasantness. The influence of the visual is not due to the aircraft size (absence of significant difference between the A320neo, and the A380). The stimuli responsible for the visual influence are those with an overcast sky (where the aircraft cannot be seen). They have been assessed less pleasant and louder, compared to the same situation (same sound) with the presence of an aircraft in the sky. The presence of clouds affects the perception of sound loudness, and pleasantness in a negative way.

The new BOLT aircraft is well accepted as much as the A320neo. Further experiments should be carried out keeping the same auralization process for all the compared aircraft. It would allow better comparisons between aircraft on timbre aspects.

Second, overall results show that participants were able to perceive the loudest aircraft. For instance, even if they were seeing the A320neo visual mixed with the sound of the A380, they were able to recognize its sound and rated this sound less pleasant and louder than the A320neo and BOLT sound syntheses.

As a conclusion, the virtual reality tool is very well tolerated by participants. They can evaluate subtle differences in audio-visual stimuli with only 2.3 dB(A) between the maximum sound levels for the three aircraft, with a shift in spectrum balance of 150Hz between the BOLT new aircraft architecture and the classical ones.

The tool is then suitable to be used for the in situ experiment to evaluate future changes in airport traffic management.

3. In situ study

3.1. Context

French Minister of ecological transition and solidarity committed to require the continuous descent for all operations 24/7 around CDG airport by 2023.

This change consists in modifying the operations during the approaching phase. Before 2023, aircraft are still allowed to approach CDG according to a stepped approach in stabilizing the aircraft elevation at a given elevation level (see Figure 32). Beginning in 2023, the stepped approach will no longer be accepted and the continuous descent will be fully implemented. Cities affected by aircraft noise and located at 25 km and more will observe aircraft passing by at higher elevation levels. Cities at lower distances from the airport should not have any modification since, at these distances, aircraft already follow the continuous descent based on ILS navigation (Instrument Landing System).

Figure 32: Diagram illustrating the difference between the stepped approach and the continuous descent for operations around CDG airport, in France. Source : DGAC

In order to ensure that the new operations fulfill the regulations in terms of safety, the air lanes are also going to be modified and will be narrowed (See Figure 33). This will involve a reduction of the overflown population.

Figure 33: Map illustrating the impact of the continuous descent operation in terms of overflight population according to the aircraft elevation. Beauchamp borders are depicted in dotted green line. FAF : Final Approach Fix, IF : Intermediate Fix, WP1(2, or 3): Way Point 1(2, or 3). Source: (DGAC)

As a result, some areas won't be overflowed anymore, and others will have an increase of flyovers at higher elevations since a concentration on narrow air lanes will be implemented.

In order to assess whether the tool is helpful in communicating to residents about potential changes, an in situ study has been organized in order to test the tool for a real case study. Two focus groups have been conducted in the city of Beauchamp 25 km away from Roissy Charles de Gaulle (CDG) airport. Since it is located close to the Initial Fix (position where aircraft start the intermediate segment of the approaching phase), many aircraft flyovers converge above Beauchamp in the configuration facing East (Figure 34). In this area, the new operation plan should not modify the number of flyovers per day since it is close to the IF.

The in-situ experiment aims to invite residents living in the city of Beauchamp to participate in a workshop, where exchanges regarding their perception about the presence of an airport near their dwelling and its impact on their quality of life has been discussed.

Figure 34: Map showing flyovers approaching Roissy CDG airport, during 1 day of March 2021 in configuration facing east. Noise exposure plan isophonic are presented in colored lines. The borders of the city of Beauchamp are depicted in grey contour. (source: ACNUSA)

During the workshop, a change affecting the approach operations was presented. This change has been introduced first in following a classical communication approach, then following the novel communication method using the VCNS simulator.

The classical method consists in an oral presentation with a few slides showing the change on maps. Some of the slides come from the French Civil Aviation Authority (DGAC) and had been previously presented at the Environmental Advisory Commission. Such commission is consulted on any matter of importance relating to the impact of the development and operation of the airport in the areas affected by the aircraft noise. The presentation describing the classical approach can be found in Appendix .

The novel approach consists in inviting each participant to use the VR equipment, the VCNS, showing 2 aircraft flyovers approaching Roissy CDG in the sky above Beauchamp park. The first flyover follows a stepped approach corresponding to the current standard around CDG airport. The second flyover simulation follows a continuous descent which should become the new standardized approach around CDG airport by 2023.

The main objective is to assess whether visualizing the change thanks to the VCNS helps communicate towards residents. Does it help understanding the impact of future airport scenarios on the resident's quality of life?

Regarding the city of Beauchamp, since it is located close to the IF, the flyover frequency should remain constant. Beauchamp residents should have an equivalent number of flyovers per day, but each flyover should be at a higher elevation following the continuous descent approach. As a result, a reduction of

the exposed aviation noise is expected when operations will all be in accordance with the continuous descent program.

3.2. Method and Material

3.2.1. Aircraft audio-visual model

For this experiment, only one aircraft model has been selected, the AIRBUS A350: a long-range, wide-body jet airliner introduced for commercialization in 2015.

The visual model has been provided by NLR (See Figure 35).

Figure 35: Aircraft AIRBUS A350 visual model

The audio sound syntheses have been simulated by AIRBUS. Two sound syntheses have been created, one simulating a stepped approach, and the other simulating a continuous descent approach (more details in Section 3.2.3).

Both sound syntheses last about 2 min. Most of the acoustic energy is below 4 kHz. All the aircraft sound sources have been considered in the auralization process (airframe, and engine noise). However, the aeroacoustic noise due to air friction (airframe noise) is the main contributor to the overall aircraft sound syntheses. A comparison of the two sound syntheses is detailed in Figure 36

Figure 36: Acoustic indicators evolution over time for 2 Airbus A350 trajectories: CDA, and Stepped approaches. SPL in dB (top left) ; SPL in dB(A) (bottom left) ; Loudness (top right) ; PNLdB (bottom right)

Both in terms of dB(A), or in sones, A350 sound synthesis is louder with the non-optimized trajectory up to $t=70$ sec. The maximum difference is reached at $t = 50$ sec and is about 2.3 dB(A) or 2 sones. One can notice an about 10 sec slot during which A350 flyover following CDA is louder (in dB(A)) than following the stepped

approach (from $t = 65$ sec to $t = 80$ sec). It has been already shown that the evolution of the sound level for continuous descent approach is not always lower than the classical approach noise level [15].

	A350 stepped	A350 CDA
Leq [dB]	59.9	59.1
Loudness [sone]	7.3	6.7
Loudness [phon]	68.7	67.5
Max SPL (@30sec) [dB]	66.0	64.2

Table 14: Global acoustic indicators (Leq, Loudness, max SPL) for the two sound auralizations (Airbus A350 flyovers with stepped approach condition and following the continuous approach condition).

Overall, A350 following the stepped approach is 0.8 dB louder and the difference in max SPL is 1.8 dB.

Other psycho-acoustic indicators are presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**

	A350 stepped	A350 CDA
EPNL [EPNdB]	73.9	72.6
N₅ [sone]	11.3	9.8
N₁₀ [sone]	10.6	9.6
L₅ [phon]	74.9	73.0
L₁₀ [phon]	74.1	72.6
L_{A,10} [dB(A)]	57.1	59.0
Max Loudness [sone]	12.4	10.8
Max Loudness [phon]	76.3	74.3
Max SPL (time step = 0.5s) [dB(A)]	60.1	58.4
Max SPL (time step = 0.5s) [dB(C)]	66.0	64.1
L_{A,eq} [dB(A)]	53.7	52.4
L_{C,eq} [dB(C)]	59.8	59.0
SEL [dB]	80.7	79.9
Spectral centroid [Hz]	317.3	296.6
Sharpness [acum]	0.70	0.69
Roughness [vacil]	0.01	0.01
Average Tonality Aures [tu]	0.08	0.07

Table 15: Acoustic and psycho-acoustic indicators for the A350 sound syntheses following the stepped approach, and following the continuous descent approach.

Spectral centroid, sharpness, roughness, and average tonality are very similar between the 2 sound syntheses. This result was expected since the same aircraft model has been used for both simulations. The main differences between the two sound syntheses are mostly found for the acoustic indicators N_5 , N_{10} , and L_{A10} , as well as in terms of max SPL.

3.2.2. Landscape

The VR experiment takes place in Beauchamp park ("parc arboré") located 24.5 km away from North Roissy CDG landing runway (See Figure 37).

Figure 37: Screenshot of the landscape VR visualization of Beauchamp park: "le parc arboré"

3.2.3. Trajectory

The listener is located at $x=24.5\text{km}$, $y=1\text{km}$, $z=1.2\text{m}$ to the runway threshold. The non-optimized procedure corresponds to a stepped approach until intersection with ILS at -20900m whereas the optimized procedure corresponds to a 1.15° slope segment until intersection with ILS at -20900m .

Figure 38: Trajectories of A350 flyovers with respect to the stepped approach (blue plain line), and to the Constant Descent Approach (dotted orange line) (Altitude vs. distance to runway) and x listener position (dotted black line)

Figure 39: Top view of the approach trajectories in plain red line (identical both for the optimized, and the non-optimized approaches). The city of Beauchamp is depicted on the map in green, and the park is depicted with a red star.

3.2.4. Background noise

The sample has been selected from the measurement campaign carried out in Paris suburb (a park in city of Beauchamp, 85 Avenue Anatole France) in September 2019 by NLR. The recording session is described in Section 2.2.6. This sound sample has been synchronized with the 360° video.

The sound sample consists in sounds of nature with the presence of birds chirping, wind, and sounds of moving leaves in trees. One car passing by at distance is also noticed.

The sample is a 1st order ambisonic recording. It has been calibrated at 45 dB(A) in terms of equivalent sound pressure level according to the calibration method described in Section 2.2.6 D p.22.

The sound analysis is carried out based the mix of the 4 channels of the ambisonic recording resulting in one mono signal analysis.

The spectrogram is presented in Figure 40. Most of the acoustic energy is below 2 kHz. Some brief slight peaks at higher frequencies (7 kHz, 8 kHz etc.) are however found corresponding to the birds chirping. The SPL evolution over time is then detailed in Figure 41.

Figure 40: Background noise Spectrogram (color bar unit is in dB)

The evolution is quite smooth and not varying much until t=60 sec. One peak is noticed at time = 70 s corresponding to a car passing by at distance.

Figure 41: Background noise sound pressure level evolution (in dB(A)) over time (blue line). Equivalent Sound Pressure Level $L_{A,eq}$ equal to 45 dB(A) is shown in dotted black line.

3.2.5. Participants

Two focus groups have been held in a meeting room owned by the city of Beauchamp. The promotion of the focus groups was carried out with the support of the municipal team through emailing to Beauchamp residents. The letter promoting the event can be found in Appendix H.

The first one took place on June 5th, 2021 and the second one took place on July 3rd, 2021 and both lasted about two hours and a half. The first session consisted in a group of four participants, all males, and the second session brought together six participants (two males, four females). Participants were given a gratification of 30 euros at the end of the meeting.

For the first focus group, all participants are Beauchamp residents whereas for the second focus group, only 4/6 are Beauchamp residents (one lives in Saint-Leu-la-Forêt, and one lives in Montigny-les-Cormeilles, two neighboring cities at the border of Beauchamp). None of the participants are members of CDG amenity group such as ADVOCNAR.

Figure 42: Picture of the participants for the second focus group.

3.2.6. Procedure

Participants were first informed of the nature of the meeting: Inform residents regarding a change in the CDG operations by 2023 affecting the aviation traffic above Beauchamp. They were also informed about the purpose of the event which is a research project aiming in the evaluation of the VR tool to ease the understanding of different scenarios in the aviation traffic.

Then, they were asked to fill consent documents. Once the paperwork signed, participants were asked to introduce themselves.

The questionnaire described in Section 3.2.6 was then used as a basis for an exchange during the first part of the focus group. Every question was recalled and every participant was invited to express his/her viewpoint. Based on the open discussion, a mood board was displayed thanks to a video projector and all the comments were added in live so that participants could see the progression in the exchanges.

After the exchange based on the questionnaire, the change regarding the CDA at CDG was presented following the classical approach (see Appendix). It consists in a presentation of a few slides based on the DGAC documentation regarding the CDA (the optimized approach). Some breaks during the presentation were proposed so that the participants could provide feedbacks on their understanding of what has been presented so far.

Once the presentation was over, a last roundtable allowed to get participants' feedbacks before going to the last part of the meeting, assessing the novel communication approach using the VR tool.

For this last part, since only one VR headset was available during the focus group, participants were able to use it only one after the other. While one participant was testing the VCNS, all the others were asked to look at the persona (see Appendix and to choose the one or those with which they relate the most.

The experience using the VR headset lasted about 5 min per participant and followed 3 steps:

1. **Non-optimized stepped approach:** participant visualized and heard the virtual environment simulating the AIRBUS A350 approach above Beauchamp park following the stepped approach according to the trajectory described in Figure 38.
2. **Optimized Constant Descent Approach (CDA):** participant visualized and heard the virtual environment simulating the AIRBUS A350 approach above Beauchamp park following the continuous descent approach according to the trajectory described in Figure 38.
3. **Switch from Stepped approach, to CDA:** participant visualized the Airbus A350 approach following the stepped approach but can switch from the stepped trajectory to CDA instantaneously in asking the student in charge of the equipment. This way, the participant could compare instantaneously and during the entire flyover the differences between the two approaches. The switch is carried out automatically every three seconds in case the participant does not ask to control the switch manually.

After each part of the VR experience, the student in charge of conducting the experiment asked a feedback to the participant.

Once all participants completed the VR experiment, three last questions were finally asked and participants could answer orally in doing some roundtables:

1. How do you perceive the proposed change?
2. And how did it sound to you?
3. Regarding the sound impact, has this tool provided additional useful information compared with the maps?

Feedbacks were once again displayed in live in the form of a mood board to all participants.

3.2.7. Material The exact same material used for the first laboratory experiment and described in Section 2.2.6 p.21 has been utilized to prepare and conduct these focus groups.

3.2.8. Questionnaire and Persona

A questionnaire was sent 1-week prior the event to all participants in order to help them prepare the discussion. The list of questions is described in Appendix I and is summarized in Table 16 below. Some questions were directly selected from a study carried out during the CIGALE project, a French research project funded by DGAC¹³.

Table 16: Summary of the preliminary questionnaire for the focus groups (translated in English)

Q1	Before the health crisis linked to the Covid-19 pandemic, describe what you heard most often in your environment. Please specify for each type of sound the place from which it is heard, the time of day, and what you are usually doing at that time.
Q2	Before the health crisis linked to the Covid-19 epidemic, describe the most disturbing sounds in your environment
Q3	What 3 words or phrases that spontaneously spring to mind when you think of airplanes ?
Q4	What 3 words or phrases that spontaneously spring to mind when you think of air traffic ?
Q5	During regular traffic periods, I am informed of the decisions and procedures put in place by the airport / state services to reduce noise pollution from aircraft. (Yes / No)
Q6	Overall, I think the decisions made by the airport are fair. You can respond on the scale below, by circling the value that best corresponds to your feelings. (0=Not at all ; 10=Yes, quite)

This questionnaire is intended for helping the participants to express their viewpoints toward the environmental sounds, and more specifically their relation with aviation noise, and aviation authorities.

Some other results from CIGALE project have been used for this ANIMA study. Based on the analysis of 1249 respondents of CIGALE study, six "persona" have

¹³ Projet Cigale : <https://explorateur.univ-toulouse.fr/gene-sonore-des-avions-lecoute-des-riverains>

been highlighted describing the types of personality of inhabitants living near airports based on their relation with air traffic. These persona are described in Appendix .

3.3. Results

3.3.1. COVID impact

Since the covid pandemic impacted air traffic at CDG, the first question was dedicated to the participants' perception regarding the potential impact(s) in the future due to the covid pandemic.

Figure 43: Mood board summarizing exchanges regarding the potential impacts of the covid pandemic in the future.

Participants expect to see durable changes in the future after the covid crisis. Some sectors should be impacted such as the financial sector, the real estate sector and the sector of online shopping. Free space in the real estate sector is going to be significantly growing due to the development of remote work.

A decrease in professional travels should reduce the air traffic market. Some participants pointed out the responsibility of human in this crisis due to our behavior toward nature. One participant recommended to change our ways of living in consuming more responsibly, more locally. Another participant pointed out the need to reduce the use of personal cars, and to develop much more collective means of transportation such as the railway sector. The very significant reduction of the air traffic during the covid crisis has been clearly perceived by all the participants. Some participants explained that they got used to this new situation with a highly reduced aviation traffic and expect to be less tolerant in the future when the traffic will return to its initial pace.

3.3.2. Relation with air traffic

The first part of the focus groups is based on the responses of the preliminary questionnaire. This set of responses provided information regarding the relation of the participants with their sound environment at home as well as their relation with air traffic, and aviation authorities.

Responses of the first question are summarized in Figure 44. The question was:

Before the health crisis linked to the Covid-19 pandemic, describe what you heard most often in your environment. Please specify for each type of sound the place

from which it is heard, the time of day, and what you are usually doing at that time.

Figure 44: Mind map summarizing the exchanges during the two focus groups regarding the sound sources they most hear from their home

Many situations have been mentioned during the talks. Some sounds are perceived positively such as the sounds of birds, or some domestic sounds in the dwelling, and other are more bothering such as the car traffic at low speeds in the street, or the freight air traffic at night. The freight air traffic is considered the most annoying sound source because it disturbs sleep. Air traffic during the day is also very often mentioned by the participants. Their exchanges showed that both the level of the sources as well as the repetition of the flyovers were making this source very annoying.

Feedbacks showed that aviation traffic at Beauchamp is a concern because it affects their quality of life causing stress, and sleep disturbance.

In order to better understand how participants do perceive the influence of air traffic noise and its impact on their quality of life, the analysis of the CIGALE portraits assessed by the participants is proposed.

Six persona have been presented, and participants were asked to select the one or those for which they relate the most.

Four participants chose Mr Satisfied as the profile they relate the most. In this group, they do not feel very annoyed by air traffic, and are satisfied that with air traffic, they can travel quickly, making the travel arrangements simpler. One participant in this group felt also close to the following persona: "Mm Joy", and "Mm not annoyed" (See Appendix).

One participant chose "Mm not annoyed" as the portrait she relates the most. She feels a bit annoyed by air traffic but feels it does not have a significant impact on her quality of life.

Then, there is another group consisting in four individuals who relate the most with "Mr Lassitude". This persona describes individuals who are annoyed by aviation traffic because it's noisy and it induces pollution. They feel they have a very limited control on this source of annoyance and feel it degrades their quality of life at home. In this group, one participant felt as close to "Mr Angry", as "Mr Lassitude". Finally, one participant relates the most with "Mr Angry". He considers air traffic to be a very harmful activity which has a very strong impact on his health. He has also a very negative attitude towards the airport. This participant expressed he feels anger because he has no control on airport authority decisions, and regrets residents living close to airport are not listened because the economic implications of the airport development are way too high. Nevertheless, he thinks that people have a role to play, fighting or collaborating with local authorities, even if he is not personally involved in associations.

Finally, our corpus of participants is heterogeneous with one group rather not annoyed because of air traffic noise, and another quite negatively affected by the presence of an airport rather close to their dwelling. None of the participants ever contacted airport authorities about land use planning and air traffic.

3.3.3. Classical communication method feedbacks

At the end of the presentation describing the CDA project and its impact for Beauchamp, participants were asked to evaluate the change, and describe what they have understood from the talk.

Overall, most participants do not expect a significant positive impact, because they understood that the flyover frequency should not be different, still with a high pace when the traffic will be recovered after the crisis. However, some participants evaluated the project not only regarding the local situation in Beauchamp, and were impressed by the reduction of overflowed population under 2000 m. According to some participants, the use of maps showing the aircraft trajectories is useful to better understand how air traffic is regulated.

Figure 45: Mind map summarizing feedbacks on the presentation of the CDA project following the classical method.

Participants appreciated to get information regarding an ongoing project at the airport. None of the participants was aware of the CDA project and its implications for the region. Communicating more with airport authorities seems potentially valuable for them. For those feeling they are not listened to, and who feel lassitude, dialogue might help better understand what is done to reduce residents' annoyance.

3.3.4. Assessing the change with immersive virtual simulations

After all participants had finished the VR experiment, a last roundtable has been initiated. Many feedbacks have been collected and are summarized in Figure 46.

The reactions can be split into 3 categories:

First, many positive feedbacks mention the VR technology as a good tool to really experience the change. The feature in the VCNS allowing to switch between 2 simulations in real time is also very appreciated because it helps to better feel the difference. Some participants who are the most annoyed and feel lassitude toward the air traffic situation in Beauchamp, expressed that learning about ongoing projects taking into account citizens' concerns contribute to improve the relations with airport authorities.

Second, negative feedbacks are highlighted regarding the CDA for CDG airport operations. According to most participants, the change is not significant, and will have a very limited impact on the quality of life for residents living in Beauchamp. Based on the participants' feedbacks, the 2 dB difference in max SPL and about 1 dB(A) difference in LAeq between the two flyovers is not enough to have a significant positive impact on the quality of life. The main reason is the absence of air traffic reduction. Such a small difference in sound level per flyover is not significant enough given the high frequency of flyovers above Beauchamp. Other negative feedbacks consider the inability of the tool to render the flyover frequency. Since part of the expressed annoyance is related to the number of flyovers per day, per evening, and per night, with the experiment using the VR headset, it was not possible to experience this aspect.

Last, some of the feedbacks suggest several ways of improvements. Some participants would have liked to feel the difference between an old aircraft versus a more recent one, with and without the optimized CDA. One participant found helpful the presence of background noise as a reference, he mentioned specifically

the car passing by at distance. He would have also liked to have voices of children playing that could have helped also to have a reference for sound levels.

Figure 46: Mind map summarizing participants reactions after they experienced the change in flyover trajectory using the VCNS simulations

3.4. Conclusion of the in situ study

The ability of a technological tool, namely the VCNS, to help communicate future airport scenarios has been studied following an in situ approach. This study aimed to invite residents discover an ongoing project that will affect air traffic and consequently exposed noise in their city Beauchamp in Paris suburb 24.5 km away from CDG runway threshold. This change consists in a modification in CDG operations imposing Continuous Descent Approaches for all operations by 2023. This will affect Beauchamp residents because aircraft will be at higher elevations when flying above Beauchamp. However, the difference is tenuous between two trajectories (optimized CDA, and traditional stepped approach) because Beauchamp is located near the IF. For example, with an Airbus A350 model, a 2 dB difference in max SPL between the CDA and the stepped approach has been predicted. For this case study, 11 participants (divided into 2 separated sessions) participated to the focus groups. These focus groups were intended for comparing two communication methods. The first one is a classical method presenting the change using maps showing the impact in terms of overflowed population according to several aircraft elevation range. The second method is based on the VCNS demonstrating the change thanks to audiovisual simulations using a virtual reality headset. The simulations were carried out in simulating the AIRBUS A350 approaches (CDA, and stepped).

Participants were divided into 2 main viewpoints toward aviation traffic. One half is annoyed by air traffic, and feels it affects their quality of life. The second group is more tolerant toward air traffic. They do not feel a significant negative impact of aircraft noise affecting their quality of life, and appreciate travelling by plane because it is very fast, and useful.

They provided mixed feedbacks for both communication methods.

Using maps to show aviation traffic helped the participants understand CDG operations. They all felt they learnt something valuable, and appreciated that it was quite clear and simple to understand. Showing the aircraft trajectories on maps was helpful to learn the air traffic operations. They were surprised by the significant reduction of overflowed population presented by the DGAC map. However, when it comes to assess the change, most participants explained that they do not expect a significant difference in the future, because the total number of flyovers per day will stay the same (unchanged), so it does not seem to affect a lot air traffic above Beauchamp. Some participants also appreciated the process of being informed of ongoing projects taking into consideration citizens' interests.

The use of the VR technology to simulate a future airport scenario was overall very well appreciated. They all agreed to say it's useful to experience the real difference between two approaches. For those skeptical regarding the change after the presentation, their opinion has been confirmed, the change will not significantly improve their quality of life based of what they experienced with the VR. Overall, they assessed that the tool is realistic, and they rely on it for simulating different flyover scenarios.

They highlighted the inability of the tool to render the flyover frequency with such limited experiment time. They also confirmed the relevance of the addition of background noise in the simulations because it helps to use it as a reference in comparing with the flyover sound syntheses.

The main limitation of the tool comes from the fatigue effect. It's not recommended to use a VR headset for a long period of time. Since the number of aircraft flyovers

per day affects the perceived annoyance, much longer experiment times would be needed to render this frequency effect which is hardly compatible with the VR technology.

Conclusion and recommendations:

Establishing good relationships between airport stakeholders and affected population is challenging. Novel technologies and simulation capabilities could help demonstrating benefits in simulating different airport scenarios. One option is the use of the Virtual Community Noise Simulator developed by NLR, as a virtual reality headset.

In order to assess the relevance of such a tool to provide credible audiovisual scenarios including aircraft flyovers, two perceptual experiments have been carried out in the frame of the ANIMA project (Subtask 3.2.3). The first experiment consisted of a perceptual test in a laboratory context, aiming at assessing the ability of the tool to render reality and audiovisual congruence. The results show that the quality of the application is very good, with 96% of the participants feeling surrounded by the environment. The new BOLT aircraft is well accepted even if it is less familiar than other aircraft. For further development of this application, the efforts should focus on the visualization of the artificial clouds and on auralization process. More landscapes representative of the diversity of the European countries should be investigated, as well as other types of aircraft architectures.

The second in-situ experiment was organized, gathering citizens of a small city around CDG airport. It aimed at experiencing the change of descent approach (from stepped to continuous) that will be fully implemented by 2023. Ten residents of Beauchamp (and two nearest cities) participated to two focus groups where the change in approach operations were described following a classical approach and using a novel method thanks to the VCNS. Both methods were judged as efficient by the participants: - with the classical approach, they appreciated to see the change of the trajectories on maps, and to learn about the number of people impacted positively (and negatively) by the change, - with the virtual reality tool, they liked hearing subtle differences in their sound environment, seeing their own landscape. Participants felt considered being invited to the meetings. They understood that Europe takes care of their quality of life. Even if they did not expect any significant noise improvement based on the CDA, they appreciated learning about the future of the airport.

It has been challenging to motivate residents to participate to the focus groups partly because of the momentary Covid situation, but probably not only. So, for authorities who want to communicate with the use of this tool, they should spend enough time advertising the event, engaging a significant number of people. Nevertheless, it is important to organize several small meetings (no more than six individuals per VR headset unit) in order to let people have time to express their feelings.

Both the laboratory experiment as well as the in situ study confirmed that the VCNS tool can be used for communication with residents around airports with a fair and trusty approach. The experiments were carried out during the sanitary crisis, so all participants appreciated the reduction of the traffic. It would be interesting to go back to people in the future to test the change of their reactions towards the aircraft flyovers when the air traffic will be back to normal.

Bibliography

- [1] R. Aalmoes, M. Boer, et H. Veerbeek, « Virtual Reality Aircraft Noise Simulation for Community Engagement », août 2018.
- [2] R. Aalmoes et M. den Boer, « Communiceren over geluid rondom windparken », *Geluid*, n° 2, p. 9-12, avr. 2017.
- [3] R. Pieren, K. Heutschi, D. Lauper, R. Zon, R. Aalmoes, et J. Lourens, « Demonstration of railway noise auralisation and visualisation ». DESTINATE, févr. 2019.
- [4] S. Rizzi, I. Legriffon, R. Pieren, et L. Bertsch, « A Comparison of Aircraft Flyover Auralizations by the Aircraft Noise Simulation Working Group », présenté à AIAA Aviation Forum 2020, Nevada, USA, juin 2020. doi: 10.2514/6.2020-2582.
- [5] J.-F. Sciabica, M. Escoufflaire, et I. Legriffon, « Results of auralization comparison », ANIMA - Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, D4.4, avr. 2019.
- [6] ASHA, « Type, degree, and, configuration of hearing loss classification ». American Speech-Language-Hearing Association, 2015.
- [7] B. Griefahn, « Determination of noise sensitivity within an internet survey using a reduced version of the Noise Sensitivity Questionnaire », *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 123, n° 5, p. 3449-3449, mai 2008, doi: 10.1121/1.2934269.
- [8] N. S. da Rocha, M. J. Power, D. M. Bushnell, et M. P. Fleck, « The EUROHIS-QOL 8-item index: comparative psychometric properties to its parent », *Value Health*, vol. 15, n° 3, p. 449-457, mai 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.jval.2011.11.035.
- [9] R. Aalmoes, « Audio-visual database », ANIMA - Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, D4.6, févr. 2020.
- [10] M. Friedman, « The Use of Ranks to Avoid the Assumption of Normality Implicit in the Analysis of Variance », *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 32, n° 200, p. 675-701, déc. 1937, doi: 10.1080/01621459.1937.10503522.
- [11] W. J. Conover et R. L. Iman, « Rank Transformations as a Bridge Between Parametric and Nonparametric Statistics », *The American Statistician*, vol. 35, n° 3, p. 124-129, 1981, doi: 10.2307/2683975.
- [12] D. Cousineau et F. O'Brien, « Error bars in within-subject designs: a comment on Baguley (2012) », *Behav Res*, vol. 46, n° 4, p. 1149-1151, déc. 2014, doi: 10.3758/s13428-013-0441-z.
- [13] P. W. M. Van Gerven, H. Vos, M. P. J. Van Boxtel, S. A. Janssen, et H. M. E. Miedema, « Annoyance from environmental noise across the lifespan », *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 126, n° 1, p. 187-194, juill. 2009, doi: 10.1121/1.3147510.
- [14] S. Lê, J. Josse, et F. Husson, « FactoMineR: An R Package for Multivariate Analysis », *J. Stat. Soft.*, vol. 25, n° 1, 2008, doi: 10.18637/jss.v025.i01.
- [15] K. White, M. Arntzen, F. Walker, F. M. Waiyaki, et M. Meeter, « Noise annoyance caused by continuous descent approaches compared to regular descent procedures », p. 194-198, 2017.
- [16] H. Møller, « Fundamentals of binaural technology », *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 36, n° 3, p. 171-218, 1992, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-682X\(92\)90046-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-682X(92)90046-U).

Appendix A

Calibration method

The calibration of the headphones was carried out in a free field situation (pink noise through a Genelec 1031A loudspeaker in front of the head) and consisted in characterizing the relationship between voltage at the headphone terminal and the corresponding binaural sound pressure. To do so, the following procedure was conducted:

- 1) A pink noise generator is set at an arbitrary level and its output voltage is measured.
- 2) 2. Small DPA 4060 microphones are set at the entrance of the ear canals of a human participant [16]. The generator is used as input of the headphones, placed over the head of the participant. The voltage at the output of the binaural microphones is measured.
- 3) 3. The headphones are removed, and the generator is used as input of Genelec 1031A loudspeaker placed at a distance of 1 meter from the participant's head. The loudspeaker's amplification is tuned until the same voltage is outputted by the binaural microphones.
- 4) 4. The head is replaced by a sound level meter to measure the sound level in dB of the loudspeaker. This corresponds to the binaural sound level produced by the headphones for the considered output voltage of the pink noise generator.

By repeating this procedure for different settings of the generator level, the relation between the logarithm of the generator output voltage and headphones playback sound level in dB is approximated as a linear function. From this information a scaling factor is applied to the aircraft sound syntheses to ensure that they are heard at the desired sound level by every listener. The resulting calibration curve is presented in Figure 47. Based on the linear interpolation of the function $\log(V_{AC\ RMS}) = f(SPL\ [dB(A)])$, the calibration of each sound synthesis can be carried out (see Table 17)

Table 17: Relations between max SPL values (in dB(A)) for the three flyover sound syntheses (BOLT, A320neo, A380) and the targeted voltage AC RMS at the soundcard output based on the headset Sennheiser HD650 calibration dataset.

		BOLT	A320neo	A380
Max SPL	[dB(A)]	66.4	66.8	68.7
Voltage AC RMS	[mV]	19.0	21.9	25.1

Figure 47: Headset Sennheiser HD650 sensitivity

Appendix B

A reduced version of the Noise Sensitivity Questionnaire (NoiSeQ), named the R-NoiSeQ [7].

The questionnaire has been presented in French and a translation in English is added. For each participant, a global rating S is calculated with respects to the following formula.

$$S = \frac{(S_1 + S_2 + S_3^* + S_4 + S_5 + S_6 + S_7 + S_8 + S_9^* + S_{10} + S_{11} + S_{12}^*)}{12} \times \frac{10}{3}$$

The participant answered the questionnaire presented in Table 18 on a 4 points scale whose modalities are: "Pas du tout d'accord (0) ; Plutôt pas d'accord (1) ; Plutôt d'accord (2); Tout à fait d'accord (3)", meaning : "Not agree at all ; Tend to disagree ; Somewhat agree ; Totally agree". The global rating S can go from 0 to 10 points (thanks to the multiplying factor $\frac{10}{3}$). For three sentences (questions 3, 9, and 12) the semantic differential is reversed and a transformation is required prior calculating the average (0→3, 1→2, 2→1, 3→0).

Table 18: Sensitivity questionnaire R-NoiSeq (French version and its English translation)

	French	English
S1	J'ai besoin d'un environnement complètement calme pour avoir une bonne nuit de sommeil.	I need a completely calm environment to get a good night's sleep.
S2	J'ai besoin d'un environnement calme pour être capable d'effectuer de nouvelles tâches.	I need a calm environment to be able to do new tasks.
S3	Quand je suis à la maison, je m'habitue rapidement au bruit.	When I'm at home, I quickly get used to the noise.
S4	Je deviens très agité(e) si j'entends quelqu'un parler alors que j'essaie de m'endormir.	I get very agitated if I hear someone talking while trying to fall asleep.
S5	Je suis très sensible au bruit de voisinage.	I am very sensitive to neighborhood noise.
S6	Lorsque les gens autour de moi sont bruyants, j'ai du mal à accomplir mon travail.	When people around me are loud, I have a hard time doing my job.
S7	Je suis nettement moins performant(e) dans les endroits bruyants.	I am much less efficient in noisy places.
S8	Je ne me sens pas bien reposé(e) lorsque la nuit précédente a été bruyante.	I don't feel well rested when the previous night was noisy.
S9	Vivre dans une rue bruyante ne me dérangerait pas.	I wouldn't mind living on a noisy street.
S10	Je suis prêt(e) à accepter des inconvénients pour vivre dans un endroit calme.	I am ready to accept inconvenience in order to live in a quiet place.
S11	J'ai besoin de calme et de tranquillité pour effectuer un travail difficile.	I need peace and quietness to do hard work.

S12 Je peux m'endormir même quand c'est bruyant. I can fall asleep even when it's noisy.

Appendix C

The EUROHIS-QOL 8-Item index according to Da Rocha [8]

Table 19: EUROHIS-QOL 8-Item index and the addition of a complementary question regarding the sound environment satisfaction at home

	French	English
QoL 1	Comment trouver-vous votre qualité de vie ?	How would you rate your quality of life?
	Très insatisfait (0)	Very unsatisfied
	Insatisfait (1)	Unsatisfied
	Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait (2)	Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied
	Satisfait (3)	Satisfied
	Très satisfait (4)	Very satisfied
QoL 2	Êtes-vous satisfait de votre santé ?	How satisfied are you with your health?
	Très insatisfait	Very unsatisfied
	Insatisfait	Unsatisfied
	Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait	Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied
	Satisfait	Satisfied
	Très satisfait	Very satisfied
QoL 3	Avez-vous suffisamment d'énergie dans votre vie quotidienne ?	Do you have enough energy for everyday life?
	Pas du tout	Not at all
	Un peu	A little
	Modérément	Moderately
	Beaucoup	A lot
	Extrêmement	Extremely
QoL 4	Êtes-vous satisfait(e) de votre capacité à effectuer les tâches de la vie quotidienne ?	How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?
	Très insatisfait	Very unsatisfied
	Insatisfait	Unsatisfied
	Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait	Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied
	Satisfait	Satisfied
	Très satisfait	Very satisfied
QoL 5	Êtes-vous satisfait(e) de vous ?	How satisfied are you with yourself?
	Très insatisfait	Very unsatisfied
	Insatisfait	Unsatisfied
	Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait	Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied
	Satisfait	Satisfied
	Très satisfait	Very satisfied
QoL 6	Êtes-vous satisfait(e) de votre relation avec les autres ?	How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?
	Très insatisfait	Very unsatisfied
	Insatisfait	Unsatisfied
	Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait	Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied

	Satisfait Très satisfait	Satisfied Very satisfied
QoL 7	Avez-vous assez d'argent pour satisfaire vos besoins ?	Have you enough money to meet your needs?
	Pas du tout Un peu Modérément Beaucoup Extrêmement	Not at all A little Moderately A lot Extremely
QoL 8	Êtes-vous satisfait(e) de votre lieu de vie ?	How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?
	Très insatisfait Insatisfait Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait Satisfait Très satisfait	Very unsatisfied Unsatisfied Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied Satisfied Very satisfied
QoL 9 (bonus)	Êtes-vous satisfait(e) de l'environnement sonore dans votre lieu de vie ?	How satisfied are you with the sound environment in your living place?
	Très insatisfait Insatisfait Ni insatisfait, ni satisfait Satisfait Très satisfait	Very unsatisfied Unsatisfied Not unsatisfied, nor satisfied Satisfied Very satisfied

Appendix D

Final questionnaire

Table 20: Final Questionnaire part 1: VR simulator overall subjective assessment

	French	English
Q1	Jusqu'à quel point ce que vous avez VU dans le monde virtuel était réaliste ?	How realistic was what you SEEN in the virtual world?
Q2	Jusqu'à quel point ce que vous avez ENTENDU dans le monde virtuel était réaliste ?	How realistic was what you heard in the virtual world?
Modalities for Q1, Q2	<i>Pas du tout réaliste (0)</i> <i>Légèrement réaliste (1)</i> <i>Moyennement réaliste (2)</i> <i>Très réaliste (3)</i> <i>Extrêmement réaliste (4)</i>	<i>Not at all realistic (1)</i> <i>Slightly realistic (2)</i> <i>Moderately realistic (3)</i> <i>Very realistic (4)</i> <i>Extremely realistic (5)</i>
Q3	Globalement, qu'avez-vous pensé de la qualité VIDEO des environnements virtuels proposés ?	In overall, what did you think of the VIDEO quality of the proposed virtual environments?
Q4	Globalement, qu'avez-vous pensé de la qualité SONORE des environnements virtuels proposés ?	Overall, what did you think of the SOUND quality of the virtual environments offered?
Q5	Qu'avez-vous pensé de la réactivité du monde virtuel suite à vos mouvements de tête ?	What did you think of the reactivity of the virtual world following your head movements?
Q6	Qu'avez-vous pensé de la restitution du mouvement de votre main maintenant la manette dans le monde virtuel ?	What did you think of the restitution of the movement of your hand holding the controller in the virtual world?
Modalities for Q3→Q6	<i>Mauvaise (1)</i> <i>Médiocre (2)</i> <i>Moyenne (3)</i> <i>Bonne (4)</i> <i>Excellente (5)</i>	<i>Bad (1)</i> <i>Poor (2)</i> <i>Average (3)</i> <i>Good (4)</i> <i>Excellent (5)</i>
Q7	Je me sentais entouré(e) par l'environnement.	I felt surrounded by the environment.
Q8	Pendant ou à l'issue de l'expérience, j'avais mal à la tête.	During or after the experience, I had a headache.
Q9	J'ai accordé plus d'attention à l'environnement qu'à mes pensées (préoccupations personnelles, rêveries, etc.).	I paid more attention to the environment than to my thoughts (personal concerns, daydreams, etc.).
Q10	Pendant ou à l'issue de l'expérience, j'avais une sensation de vertige.	During or after the experience, I had a feeling of vertigo.

Q11	J'avais l'impression d'être physiquement présent(e) dans l'environnement.	I felt like I was physically present in the environment.
Q12	J'ai ressenti une sensation de mal de cœur durant l'expérience.	I felt a feeling of sickness during the experience.
Q13	Je sentais que l'environnement réagissait correctement aux actions que j'accomplissais	I felt that the environment was reacting correctly to the actions I was performing.
Modalities for Q7→Q13	<i>Pas du tout d'accord</i> (1)	<i>Not agree at all</i> (1)
	<i>Plutôt pas d'accord</i> (2)	<i>Rather disagree</i> (2)
	<i>Indifférent</i> (3)	<i>Indifferent</i> (3)
	<i>Plutôt d'accord</i> (4)	<i>Somewhat agree</i> (4)
	<i>Tout à fait d'accord</i> (5)	<i>Totally agree</i> (5)
Q14	Champs libre	Free comments

Table 21: Final Questionnaire – 4st part : General information

	French	English
Q15	J'ai l'habitude d'utiliser les équipements de réalité virtuelle.	I am used to using virtual reality equipment.
Q16	J'ai l'habitude de voir passer des avions autour de chez moi.	I am used to seeing planes passing by my house.
Q17	J'ai l'habitude de jouer à des jeux vidéo.	I am used to playing video games.
Modalities for Q15→Q17	<i>Pas du tout d'accord</i> (1)	<i>Not agree at all</i> (1)
	<i>Plutôt pas d'accord</i> (2)	<i>Rather disagree</i> (2)
	<i>Indifférent</i> (3)	<i>Indifferent</i> (3)
	<i>Plutôt d'accord</i> (4)	<i>Somewhat agree</i> (4)
	<i>Tout à fait d'accord</i> (5)	<i>Totally agree</i> (5)
Additional information		
Q18	Age	
Q19	Zip code	
Q20	Gender	

Appendix E

Stimuli Order

Nomenclature :

AC1	BOLT Visual model	S1	BOLT sound s
AC2	A380 Visual model	S2	A380 sound s
AC3	A320neo Visual model	S3	A320neo sou
Clouds	Absence of aircraft due to cloudy sky		

Subject ID	Landscape	Loc 1											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Su1	Urban/Park	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S1
Su2	Park/Urban	Clouds S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1
Su3	Urban/Park	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S1
Su4	Park/Urban	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3
Su5	Urban/Park	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2
Su6	Park/Urban	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3
Su7	Urban/Park	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2
Su8	Park/Urban	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S2
Su9	Urban/Park	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3
Su10	Park/Urban	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1
Su11	Urban/Park	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S3
Su12	Park/Urban	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2
Su13	Urban/Park	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S3
Su14	Park/Urban	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1
Su15	Urban/Park	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2
Su16	Park/Urban	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3
Su17	Urban/Park	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S3
Su18	Park/Urban	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2
Su19	Urban/Park	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1
Su20	Park/Urban	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3
Su21	Urban/Park	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1
Su22	Park/Urban	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3
Su23	Urban/Park	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S1
Su24	Park/Urban	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S1
Su25	Urban/Park	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3
Su26	Park/Urban	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S2
Su27	Urban/Park	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1
Su28	Park/Urban	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2
Su29	Urban/Park	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S1
Su30	Park/Urban	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2
Su31	Urban/Park	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S2

Su32	Park/Urban6	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3
Su33	Urban/Park	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S2
Su34	Park/Urban7	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S3
Su35	Urban/Park	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S3
Su36	Park/Urban8	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S3
Su37	Urban/Park	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S3
Su38	Park/Urban	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S1
Su39	Urban/Park	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S2
Su40	Park/Urban	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2
Su41	Urban/Park	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3
Su42	Park/Urban	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1
Su43	Urban/Park	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3
Su44	Park/Urban	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2
Su45	Urban/Park	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1
Su46	Park/Urban	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1
Su47	Urban/Park	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1
Su48	Park/Urban	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1
Su49	Urban/Park	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2
Su50	Park/Urban	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S1
Su51	Urban/Park	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1
Su52	Park/Urban	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2
Su53	Urban/Park	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S3
Su54	Park/Urban	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2
Su55	Urban/Park	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1
Su56	Park/Urban	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S3
Su57	Urban/Park	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2
Su58	Park/Urban	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2
Su59	Urban/Park	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1
Su60	Park/Urban	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2

		Loc 2											
		13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
S1	Urban/Park	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1
S2	Park/Urban	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S1
S3	Urban/Park	Clouds S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1
S4	Park/Urban	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S1
S5	Urban/Park	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3
S6	Park/Urban	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2
S7	Urban/Park	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3
S8	Park/Urban	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2
S9	Urban/Park	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S2
S10	Park/Urban	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3
S11	Urban/Park	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1
S12	Park/Urban	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S3
S13	Urban/Park	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2
S14	Park/Urban	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S3
S15	Urban/Park	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1
S16	Park/Urban	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2
S17	Urban/Park	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3
S18	Park/Urban	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S3
S19	Urban/Park	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2
S20	Park/Urban	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1
S21	Urban/Park	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3
S22	Park/Urban	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1
S23	Urban/Park	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3
S24	Park/Urban	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S1
S25	Urban/Park	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S1
S26	Park/Urban	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3
S27	Urban/Park	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S2
S28	Park/Urban	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1
S29	Urban/Park	AC1 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2
S30	Park/Urban	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S1
S31	Urban/Park	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2
S32	Park/Urban6	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S2
S33	Urban/Park	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3
S34	Park/Urban7	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S2
S35	Urban/Park	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S3
S36	Park/Urban8	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S3
S37	Urban/Park	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S3
S38	Park/Urban	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S3
S39	Urban/Park	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC1 S1

S40	Park/Urban	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S2
S41	Urban/Park	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2
S42	Park/Urban	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S3
S43	Urban/Park	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1
S44	Park/Urban	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3
S45	Urban/Park	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S2
S46	Park/Urban	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1
S47	Urban/Park	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1
S48	Park/Urban	AC2 S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	AC2 S1	AC3 S3
S49	Urban/Park	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC3 S1
S50	Park/Urban	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	Clouds S2
S51	Urban/Park	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S1
S52	Park/Urban	AC1 S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S3	AC1 S2	Clouds S1
S53	Urban/Park	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S3	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC3 S3	Clouds S2
S54	Park/Urban	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S2	AC2 S3
S55	Urban/Park	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC2 S2	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	Clouds S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC2 S3	AC3 S2
S56	Park/Urban	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	AC1 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2
S57	Urban/Park	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S2	Clouds S1	AC1 S3	Clouds S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S3
S58	Park/Urban	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC3 S2	AC2 S1	Clouds S2	AC2 S3	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2
S59	Urban/Park	AC2 S1	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	AC2 S2	AC1 S1	AC3 S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1	AC1 S2	AC3 S1	AC2 S3	Clouds S2
S60	Park/Urban	AC2 S3	AC1 S1	AC2 S2	AC3 S1	AC1 S2	AC2 S1	AC3 S2	Clouds S3	AC3 S3	Clouds S2	AC1 S3	Clouds S1

Appendix F

ANOVA tables for global pleasantness

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
AgeCat	1, 56	3742.42	2.95 +	.039	.092
A.C.Sound	1.25, 70.17	165.95	40.60 ***	.030	<.001
AgeCat:A.C.Sound	1.25, 70.17	165.95	5.08 *	.004	.020
A.C.Visual	2.62, 146.60	162.54	9.27 ***	.014	<.001
AgeCat:A.C.Visual	2.62, 146.60	162.54	1.24	.002	.295
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.91, 274.78	99.15	0.13	<.001	.984
AgeCat:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.91, 274.78	99.15	0.48	<.001	.786

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
Sens.Cat	1, 56	3605.54	5.18 *	.066	.027
A.C.Sound	1.27, 71.21	174.07	39.24 ***	.032	<.001
Sens.Cat:A.C.Sound	1.27, 71.21	174.07	1.38	.001	.252
A.C.Visual	2.53, 141.51	166.71	9.41 ***	.015	<.001
Sens.Cat:A.C.Visual	2.53, 141.51	166.71	1.82	.003	.156
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.91, 275.09	98.69	0.18	<.001	.968
Sens.Cat:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.91, 275.09	98.69	0.68	.001	.637

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
Gender	1, 56	3867.38	1.04	.014	.312
A.C.Sound	1.27, 70.88	178.93	36.10 ***	.028	<.001
Gender:A.C.Sound	1.27, 70.88	178.93	0.08	<.001	.830
A.C.Visual	2.60, 145.66	166.48	8.57 ***	.013	<.001
Gender:A.C.Visual	2.60, 145.66	166.48	0.25	<.001	.834
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.89, 273.94	98.99	0.14	<.001	.982
Gender:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.89, 273.94	98.99	0.75	.001	.586

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
QL.Cat	3, 54	4030.21	0.25	.011	.864
A.C.Sound	1.27, 68.35	170.43	18.66 ***	.014	<.001
QL.Cat:A.C.Sound	3.80, 68.35	170.43	1.63	.004	.181
A.C.Visual	2.59, 139.86	167.16	4.60 **	.007	.006
QL.Cat:A.C.Visual	7.77, 139.86	167.16	0.75	.004	.641
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.84, 261.33	98.65	1.05	.002	.389
QL.Cat:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	14.52, 261.33	98.65	1.19	.006	.284

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
AcFamiliarity	2, 55	3740.90	1.98	.052	.147
A.C.Sound	1.27, 69.83	174.85	19.87 ***	.016	<.001
AcFamiliarity:A.C.Sound	2.54, 69.83	174.85	1.11	.002	.346
A.C.Visual	2.60, 143.18	167.99	5.55 **	.009	.002
AcFamiliarity:A.C.Visual	5.21, 143.18	167.99	0.35	.001	.889
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.85, 266.59	100.23	0.47	<.001	.795
AcFamiliarity:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	9.69, 266.59	100.23	0.78	.003	.642

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
VrFamiliarity	2, 55	3968.90	0.29	.008	.749
A.C.Sound	1.27, 69.59	179.79	22.54 ***	.018	<.001
VrFamiliarity:A.C.Sound	2.53, 69.59	179.79	0.42	<.001	.708
A.C.Visual	2.59, 142.32	167.79	6.72 ***	.010	<.001
VrFamiliarity:A.C.Visual	5.18, 142.32	167.79	0.55	.002	.745
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.87, 268.03	100.15	0.43	<.001	.826
VrFamiliarity:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	9.75, 268.03	100.15	0.65	.002	.764

Effect	df	MSE	F	ges	p.value
VideoGamesFamiliarity	2, 55	3963.65	0.33	.009	.722
A.C.Sound	1.25, 68.67	176.85	32.54 ***	.025	<.001
VideoGamesFamiliarity:A.C.Sound	2.50, 68.67	176.85	1.26	.002	.294
A.C.Visual	2.58, 141.88	168.99	6.76 ***	.010	<.001
VideoGamesFamiliarity:A.C.Visual	5.16, 141.88	168.99	0.44	.001	.828
A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	4.87, 267.94	100.56	0.27	<.001	.925
VideoGamesFamiliarity:A.C.Sound:A.C.Visual	9.74, 267.94	100.56	0.55	.002	.853

Appendix G

Presentation for the situ study at the workshop in the city of Beauchamp

LA DESCENTE DOUCE H24

ÉVALUATION OPÉRATIONNELLE À PARIS-CHARLES DE GAULLE

CONTEXTE

VERS DES DESCENTES DOUCES H24

Dans le cadre des Assises Nationales du Transport Aérien, la ministre de la Transition écologique et solidaire a annoncé le déploiement opérationnel du concept des descentes douces H24 à Paris-Charles de Gaulle à l'horizon 2023.

Pour mettre en œuvre ces procédures sur l'aéroport de Paris-Charles de Gaulle, la Direction des services de la Navigation Aérienne (DSNA) travaille à la mise en place d'un concept de **navigation basée sur la performance**, utilisant des données de positionnement satellitaire jusqu'à l'interception de l'axe d'approche (procédure « PBN »), puis un guidage par ILS (Instrument Landing System) pour la phase finale.

Ce concept vise à rendre indépendantes les approches des deux doublets de pistes pour permettre la réalisation de **descentes douces H24**.

PRÉREQUIS

La réalisation des descentes douces H24 ne sera réalisable que si les conditions suivantes sont respectées :

- **Indépendance des deux doublets** de pistes en toute sécurité lors d'arrivées simultanées.
- Précision de navigation sur la **procédure PBN**.
- **100% des avions équipés** des moyens de navigation satellitaire.

PROJET

EXEMPLE FACE A L'EST

Survols en configuration Est de la commune de Beauchamp (95) et des trames vertes et bleues l'environnant (Journée type - 02/03/2021)

Légende

Emprises administratives

- Contours de Beauchamp (95)
- Contours des autres communes
- Emprise des pistes d'aéroport
- Limite de VPE

Trajectoires de survol des aéronefs dans une journée type

- Départ de Paris - Orly
- Arrivée de Paris - Orly
- Départ de Paris - Charles-de-Gaulle
- Arrivée de Paris - Charles-de-Gaulle
- Départ de Paris - Le Bourget
- Arrivée de Paris - Le Bourget

Courbes isophones du PEB

- Zone A (Lden >70)
- Zone B (62 < Lden < 65)
- Zone C (55 < Lden < 57)
- Zone D (Lden = 50)

Trames Vertes et Bleues (BDTopo IGN)

- Surface hydrographique
- Forêt publique
- Zone de végétation

Auteur : Pôle Technique de l'ACNUSA - 28/05/2021
Sources : DGAC, BDTopo, OpenStreetMap

PROJET FINAL DESCENTES DOUCES

LA DESCENTE DOUCE H24 À PARIS-CHARLES DE GAULLE |

Projet d'organisation des flux en descentes douces en cours d'études

GAINS DU PROJET FINAL

-70%
Nombre de personnes
survolées sous 2000 m

GAINS

- Descentes douces 7/7
- Standardisation des interceptions ILS
- Diminution des avions en inter-pistes à basse altitude.
- Réduction de la dispersion des avions permettant de diminuer le nombre de riverains survolés.
- Réduction des impacts environnementaux, acoustiques et gazeux.

-85%
Réduction des vols
en inter-pistes
en basse altitude

*Réalisation de campagnes de mesurage sonore lors des Live Trials, de janvier à mars 2021.

LA DESCENTE DOUCE H24 À PARIS-CHARLES DE GAULLE |

Merci pour votre attention

Avez-vous des questions ?

GLOSSAIRE

CCE : Commission Consultative de l'Environnement

Descente douce : L'approche en descente douce est une technique qui permet aux pilotes de conduire le vol à l'arrivée en évitant les paliers.

Doublets de piste : Pistes parallèles d'un aéroport. Paris-Charles de Gaulle dispose de deux doublets de pistes parallèles, un doublet Nord et un doublet Sud.

IF (Initial Fix) : Début du segment intermédiaire, l'avion adopte sa configuration pour l'atterrissage.

FAF (Final Approach Fix) : Repère d'approche finale, l'avion débute sa descente finale.

ILS (Instrument Landing System) : Instrument d'aide à l'atterrissage utilisé par tous les avions opérant sur les principaux aéroports. Il apporte au pilote un guidage vertical et horizontal jusqu'à l'atterrissage quelles que soient les conditions météorologiques.

PBN (Performance Based Navigation) : ou navigation de précision, est un système basé sur la performance de navigation. Le suivi de la navigation par satellites permet une grande précision et une meilleure prédictibilité des trajectoires.

Appendix H

Communication letter to Beauchamp residents

Résumé : Organisation d'une rencontre avec des membres d'association de riverains afin d'échanger sur votre relation en tant qu'habitant de Beauchamp avec l'aéroport Roissy Charles de Gaulle

Où et quand : Le samedi xx/xx de 10h à 12h

Dans le cadre d'un projet de recherche européen (projet [ANIMA](#)), l'université de CY Cergy Paris souhaite organiser plusieurs rencontres avec des habitants de la ville Beauchamp pour échanger sur votre perception de l'aéroport Roissy Charles de Gaulle.

Ces rencontres donneront l'occasion d'échanger sur l'ensemble des aspects (positifs et négatifs) relatifs à la présence de cet aéroport assez proche de votre domicile.

L'une de ces sessions sera dédiée à des habitants membres d'une association de riverains. Elle réunira 6 habitants pour échanger pendant 2h environ.

Avec l'accord de la mairie, cette rencontre se déroulera dans l'espace XXXX situé au XXXXXXXXXXXX, au cœur de votre ville.

Elle aura lieu le samedi xx/xx, et commencera à 10h.

Si vous êtes intéressés pour exprimer votre avis sur votre relation avec l'aéroport et découvrir un projet de recherche novateur, merci de prendre contact avec nous par téléphone ou email.

Bien cordialement,

Professeur Catherine Lavandier

Contact pour inscription :

Romain Dedieu

Romain.dedieu1@cyu.fr

Appendix I

Preliminary questionnaire for the focus groups

Dans le cadre du projet de recherche européen ANIMA (<https://anima-project.eu/>), le laboratoire ETIS de CY Cergy Paris Université organise des rencontres avec des habitants de la ville de Beauchamp pour échanger sur la façon dont ils perçoivent leur qualité de vie, en rapport à la présence de l'aéroport Roissy Charles de Gaulle dans leur environnement.

Vous avez accepté de participer à ces rencontres et nous vous en remercions. Au début de l'atelier nous allons échanger sur les ressentis des participants vis-à-vis de leur environnement. Pour vous y préparer, nous vous proposons de répondre à ces questions, et de venir à l'atelier avec le questionnaire rempli.

Notez que le questionnaire sera remis aux chercheurs à la fin de la réunion.

Q1. Avant la crise sanitaire liée à l'épidémie du Covid-19, décrivez **ce que vous entendiez le plus souvent dans votre environnement**. Pour vous aider, remplissez les rubriques du tableau ci-dessous en précisant pour chaque type de son l'endroit depuis lequel il est entendu, le moment de la journée, et ce que vous faites à ce moment-là.

Vous pouvez citer jusqu'à 3 types de sons.

Type de son	Lieu	Moment	Activité

Q2. Avant la crise sanitaire liée à l'épidémie du Covid-19, décrivez les sons **les plus gênants** dans votre environnement. Pour cela, remplissez les rubriques du tableau ci-dessous. Vous pouvez citer jusqu'à 3 types de sons.

Type de son	Lieu	Moment	Activité

Q3. Quels sont les 3 mots ou expressions qui vous viennent spontanément à l'esprit quand vous pensez aux **avions** ? Pour répondre, utilisez les cases ci-dessous.

Vous pouvez vous appuyer sur vos expériences connues et/ou vécues en lien avec les **avions**. Cela peut référer aussi bien à des objets, des activités, des ressentis, des lieux, etc.

1	
2	
3	

Q4. Quels sont les 3 mots ou expressions qui vous viennent spontanément à l'esprit quand vous pensez au **trafic aérien** ? Pour répondre, utilisez les cases ci-dessous.

Vous pouvez vous appuyer sur vos expériences connues et/ou vécues en lien avec le **trafic aérien**. Cela peut référer aussi bien à des objets, des activités, des ressentis, des lieux, etc.

1	
2	
3	

Q5. En période de trafic régulier, je suis informé.e des décisions et procédures mises en place par l'aéroport / les services de l'État pour réduire les nuisances sonores liées aux avions.

OUI
 NON

Si OUI :

Globalement, je trouve que les décisions prises par l'aéroport sont justes. Vous pouvez répondre sur l'échelle ci-dessous, en entourant la valeur qui correspond le mieux à votre ressenti

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Non, pas du tout									Oui, tout à fait	

Q7. Avez-vous déjà sollicité l'aéroport /les services de l'État pour lui/leur faire part d'une gêne ressentie ?

OUI
 NON

Si vous avez répondu « OUI » à Q7

Q8. Précisez pour quel motif.

.....

.....

.....

.....

Si vous avez répondu « OUI » à Q7

Q9. Merci de bien vouloir répondre aux affirmations suivantes en utilisant l'échelle allant de 0 (Non pas du tout) à 10 (Oui tout à fait).

– En règle générale mes demandes sont prises en compte

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Non, pas du tout									Oui, tout à fait	

– J'ai le sentiment d'être entendu.e lorsque je fais part de mes difficultés

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Non, pas du tout									Oui, tout à fait	

Q10. Avez-vous des demandes particulières que vous souhaitez aborder lors de notre réunion ?

.....

.....

.....

Appendix J

Persona summary from CIGALE project

1) Mr Sadness

SA VISION DU TRAFIC AÉRIEN

- . A L'IMPRESSION FORTE D'ÊTRE TRAITÉ JUSTEMENT PAR L'AÉROPORT
- . A LE SENTIMENT DE PARTICIPER AUX DÉCISIONS LIÉES À L'AÉROPORT ET QUE SON AVIS EST ENTENDU

SON RESENTI PAR RAPPORT AU BRUIT DES AVIONS

- . A LE SENTIMENT QUE L'AVION IMPACTE SA SANTÉ
- . CONSIDÈRE QUE SON ENVIRONNEMENT SONORE QUOTIDIEN EST UN PROBLÈME
- . SE SENT TRISTE QUAND IL EST SURVOLÉ PARCE QUE ÇA LUI DONNE ENVIE DE PARTIR MAIS ÇÀ LUI RAPPELLE AUSSI LA POLLUTION

SA QUALITE DE VIE

- . N'EST PAS VRAIMENT SATISFAIT DE SA VIE
- . PENSE N'ÊTRE PAS EN BONNE SANTÉ

SA FACON DE REAGIR AUX PROBLEMES

- . A LE SENTIMENT D'AVOIR UN FAIBLE CONTRÔLE SUR SA VIE

2) Mr Satisfied

SA VISION DU TRAFIC AERIEN

- . A UNE ATTITUDE POSITIVE PAR RAPPORT À L'AÉROPORT
- . LE TRAFIC AÉRIEN EST ASSOCIÉ À UN MOYEN DE TRANSPORT RAPIDE, PRATIQUE ET FACILITANT

SON RESENTI PAR RAPPORT AU BRUIT DES AVIONS

- . A L'IMPRESSON D'ÊTRE TRAITÉ JUSTEMENT PAR L'AÉROPORT
- . A LE SENTIMENT QUE L'AVION IMPACTE FORTEMENT SA SANTÉ
- . A LE SENTIMENT DE PARTICIPER AUX DÉCISIONS LIÉES À L'AÉROPORT
- . DÉFINIT LA GÊNE SONORE PAR LA FRÉQUENCE D'APPARITION D'UN BRUIT

SA QUALITE DE VIE

- . EST VRAIMENT SATISFAIT DE SA VIE
- . PENSE ÊTRE EN BONNE SANTÉ
- . A UN RESENTI POSITIF DE SON ENVIRONNEMENT SONORE QUOTIDIEN
- . MET EN PLACE DES PRATIQUES ECOLOGIQUES AU QUOTIDIEN

SA FACON DE REAGIR AUX PROBLEMES

- . A UN FORT SENTIMENT DE CONTRÔLE

3) Mr Weariness

SA VISION DU TRAFIC AÉRIEN

- . A UNE ATTITUDE NÉGATIVE VIS-À-VIS DE L'AÉROPORT
- . CONSIDÈRE LE TRAFIC AÉRIEN COMME UNE ACTIVITÉ NUISIBLE ET NE SOUHAITE PAS QU'ELLE REPRENNE POUR DES RAISONS QUI CONCERNENT SA VIE PERSONNELLE
- . L'AVION EST ASSOCIÉ AU BRUIT ET GÉNÈRE DE LA POLLUTION
- . A UNE REPRÉSENTATION NÉGATIVE DU TRAFIC AÉRIEN ASSOCIÉE À DES PEURS ET AU STRESS

SON RESENTI PAR RAPPORT AU BRUIT DES AVIONS

- . A LE SENTIMENT QUE L'AVION IMPACTE FORTEMENT SA SANTÉ
- . N'A PAS L'IMPRESSIION D'ÊTRE TRAITÉ JUSTEMENT PAR L'AÉROPORT
- . RESSENT DU DÉGOÛT ET DE LA COLÈRE LORSQU'IL EST SURVOLÉ
- . N'A PAS LE SENTIMENT QUE SON AVIS EST ENTENDU PAR L'AÉROPORT

SA QUALITE DE VIE

- . N'EST GLOBALEMENT PAS SATISFAIT DE SA VIE
- . PENSE N'ÊTRE VRAIMENT PAS EN BONNE SANTÉ
- . IL EST DÉGOÛTÉ ET SE SENT EN COLÈRE LORSQU'IL EST SURVOLÉ

SA FACON DE REAGIR AUX PROBLEMES

- . TRÈS FAIBLE SENTIMENT DE CONTRÔLE
- . MET EN PLACE DES STRATÉGIES DE FAIRE-FACE À COURT TERME CENTRÉE SUR LA DIMINUTION DU SON

4) Mm Not Annoyed

SA VISION DU TRAFIC AERIEN

- . A UNE ATTITUDE POSITIVE PAR RAPPORT À L'AÉROPORT
- . A UNE REPRÉSENTATION POSITIVE DE L'AVION Tournée VERS LE VOYAGE, L'ÉVASION, LE DÉPAYSEMENT

SON RESSENTI PAR RAPPORT AU BRUIT DES AVIONS

- . N'A PAS LE SENTIMENT QUE L'AVION IMPACTE SA SANTÉ
- . A PLUTÔT LE SENTIMENT D'ÊTRE TRAITÉE JUSTEMENT PAR L'AÉROPORT

SA QUALITE DE VIE

- . NE MET PAS EN ŒUVRE DE PRATIQUES ECOLOGIQUES AU QUOTIDIEN

SA FACON DE REAGIR AUX PROBLEMES

- . A LE SENTIMENT D'AVOIR UN FAIBLE CONTRÔLE SUR SA VIE
- . N'A PAS DE STRATÉGIE DE FAIRE-FACE CAR ELLE N'EST PAS GÊNÉE

5) Mm Angry

SA VISION DU TRAFIC AÉRIEN

- . A UNE ATTITUDE TRÈS NÉGATIVE VIS-À-VIS DE L'AÉROPORT
- . CONSIDÈRE LE TRAFIC AÉRIEN COMME UNE ACTIVITÉ NUISIBLE ET NE SOUHAITE PAS QU'ELLE REPRENNE POUR DES RAISONS QUI CONCERNE SA VIE PERSONNELLE
- . L'AVION ET LE TRAFIC AÉRIEN EST ASSOCIÉ AU BRUIT ET GÉNÈRE DE LA POLLUTION
- . LE TRAFIC AÉRIEN EST ÉVOCATEUR DE PEUR ET DE STRESS

SON RESENTI PAR RAPPORT AU BRUIT DES AVIONS

- . A LE SENTIMENT QUE L'AVION IMPACTE TRÈS FORTEMENT SA SANTÉ
- . N'A PAS DU TOUT L'IMPRESSION D'ÊTRE TRAITÉ JUSTEMENT PAR L'AÉROPORT NI QUE SON AVIS SOIT ENTENDU
- . SIGNALE LA FRÉQUENCE ET LA GÊNE DES SONS D'AVION DANS SON ENVIRONNEMENT SONORE QUOTIDIEN
- . GÊNE SONORE VÉCU COMME UNE INTRUSION, COMME UNE AGRESSION QUI EMPÊCHE LE BIEN-ÊTRE PHYSIQUE ET PSYCHIQUE

SA QUALITE DE VIE

- . PENSE NE PAS ÊTRE EN BONNE SANTÉ
- . SE SENT EN COLÈRE LORSQU'ELLE EST SURVOLÉE
- . MET EN PLACE DES PRATIQUES ECOLOGIQUES AU QUOTIDIEN

SA FACON DE REAGIR AUX PROBLEMES

- . POSSÈDE UN FORT SENTIMENT DE CONTRÔLE
- . MET EN PLACE DES STRATÉGIES DE FAIRE-FACE À LONG TERME CENTRÉ SUR LE DÉPÔT DE PLAINTES ET À COURT TERME CENTRÉES SUR COUVRIR, ÉLOIGNER OU DIMINUER LE BRUIT
- . SE SENT DÉCOURAGÉ AVEC PEU DE MARGES DE MANOEUVRE

6) Mm Joy

SA VISION DU TRAFIC AERIEN

- . A UNE ATTITUDE TRÈS POSITIVE PAR RAPPORT À L'AÉROPORT
- . A UNE REPRÉSENTATION POSITIVE DE L'AVION ET DU TRAFIC AÉRIEN CAR IL REPRÉSENTE LE VOYAGE, L'ÉVASION ET LE DÉPAYSEMENT
- . PARMIS LES ACTIVITÉS QU'ELLE SOUHAITE VOIR REPRENDRE, LE TRAFIC AÉRIEN OCCUPE UNE PLACE PRIVILÉGIÉE POUR DES RAISONS QUI LA CONCERNENT INDIVIDUELLEMENT

SON RESENTI PAR RAPPORT AU BRUIT DES AVIONS

- . A FORTEMENT L'IMPRESSION D'ÊTRE TRAITÉE JUSTEMENT PAR L'AÉROPORT
- . N'A PAS LE SENTIMENT QUE L'AVION IMPACTE SA SANTÉ
- . RESSENT DE LA JOIE QUAND ELLE EST SURVOLÉE CAR ELLE PENSE AU VOYAGE

SA QUALITE DE VIE

- . PENSE ÊTRE EN BONNE SANTÉ
- . MET EN PLACE QUELQUES PRATIQUES ECOLOGIQUES AU QUOTIDIEN

SA FACON DE REAGIR AUX PROBLEMES

- . N'A PAS DE STRATÉGIE DE FAIRE-FACE CAR N'EST PAS GÊNÉE

Appendix K

Ethical comity validation (ad-hoc)

Pr. Frédéric Vidal
Vice-Président à la Recherche de CY Cergy Paris Université
frederic.vidal@cyu.fr

Cergy-Pontoise, le 9 octobre 2020

Objet : Avis sur le projet « *Etude de la perception des riverains aux bruits des survols des avions à l'aide d'un outil de réalité virtuelle* »

Catherine Lavandier, professeure à CY Cergy Paris Université et membre du laboratoire ETIS, a présenté pour validation par le comité d'éthique les protocoles de recherche prévus dans le cadre du projet européen ANIMA (Aircraft Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches). La demande concerne un test perceptif effectué à l'aide d'un outil de réalité virtuelle, où les participants sont plongés dans divers cadres audio-visuels (paysage urbain ou rural, passage de divers avions actuels mais aussi du futur). L'objectif de ce test est de démontrer la validité écologique de cet outil de réalité virtuelle dans des contextes d'évaluation perceptive de passages d'avions.

Etant donné que le comité d'éthique de CY Cergy Paris Université est en cours de constitution, afin de pouvoir répondre à la demande urgente de la Pr. Lavandier, un comité *ad-hoc* a été constitué pour étudier le dossier. Ce comité est composé de deux enseignants chercheurs qui feront partie du futur comité d'éthique (dont un spécialiste en droit), de la référente à la protection des données (DPO) de l'établissement et du vice-président adjoint à la recherche, en charge de la constitution du comité d'éthique de CY Cergy Paris Université.

L'examen du dossier a mis en évidence un projet de recherche non interventionnelle, sans danger pour les participants, dont les objectifs de la recherche respectent les critères éthiques et qui suit toutes les règles de conduite des protocoles expérimentaux, en termes de recrutement, d'information, de consentement des participants et de protection des données personnelles.

Par conséquent, le comité *ad-hoc* a donné un avis favorable à la demande de la professeure Catherine Lavandier.

Pr. Frédéric Vidal
Vice-Président à la Recherche

Appendix L

Information document – Laboratory experiment

FICHE D'INFORMATION DU PARTICIPANT

IL VOUS SERA FOURNI UNE COPIE DE CETTE FICHE D'INFORMATION

Titre de l'Étude : ***Etude d'une nouvelle méthode de sensibilisation des riverains aux bruits d'avion : la réalité virtuelle***

Laboratoire ETIS, UMR 8051,
CY Cergy Paris Université, ENSEA, CNRS

Noms et informations de contact des chercheurs :

- Romain Dedieu (romain.dedieu1@cyu.fr)
- Catherine Lavandier (catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr)

Nom et information de contact du chercheur principal :

Catherine Lavandier (catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr)

Tel: 01 34 25 68 39

1. Paragraphe d'invitation

Vous êtes invité à prendre part à un projet de recherche conduit par les membres du laboratoire ETIS dans le cadre du projet européen ANIMA (Aircraft Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches). Avant que vous ne confirmiez votre participation à cette expérience, il est important que vous compreniez pourquoi ces travaux sont menés et ce que votre participation implique. **Cette étude est sans risque pour vous, car elle implique seulement une expérience de réalité virtuelle de passages d'avions sur lesquels il vous sera posé une série de questions.** Votre participation est totalement volontaire. Prenez le temps de lire attentivement les informations suivantes, n'hésitez pas à en discuter avec d'autres si vous le désirez. Demandez-nous si quelque chose ne vous semble pas clair ou si vous souhaitez plus d'informations. Prenez le temps de décider si oui ou non vous souhaitez prendre part à cette expérience. **Nous vous remercions de votre attention.**

2. Quel est le but de cette étude ?

Dans le cadre du projet européen ANIMA (<https://anima-project.eu>), de nouveaux outils de communication avec les riverains sont étudiés (réseaux sociaux, application mobile, réalité virtuelle). L'objectif de ce test est d'étudier si la réalité virtuelle est une bonne solution

technologique pour évaluer des passages d'avions variés. Les dimensions visuelles et auditives seront évaluées.

3. Pourquoi ai-je été choisi ?

Vous avez été choisi parce que vous faites partie des personnes qui ont répondu favorablement à notre annonce. Pour notre étude, nous souhaitons recruter approximativement 60 participants et avoir un échantillon raisonnablement équilibré en termes d'âge et de genre. Si vous présentez un sévère trouble de l'audition, nous vous déconseillons de participer car cela pourrait affecter nos résultats.

4. Dois-je participer ?

La participation à cette expérience est totalement volontaire. C'est à vous de décider si vous souhaitez ou non prendre part à cette expérience. Si vous décidez d'y prendre part, vous garderez cette fiche d'information avec vous, et il vous sera demandé de signer un formulaire de consentement. Vous pouvez vous retirer à tout moment de l'expérience sans donner de raison. Si vous décidez de vous retirer, il vous sera demandé que faire des données déjà collectées.

5. A quoi dois-je m'attendre si je participe ?

Si vous rejoignez cette étude, vous passerez un audiogramme (examen qui permet de caractériser la qualité de votre audition), puis vous écouterez un certain nombre de situations extérieures au travers d'un casque de réalité virtuelle que nous mettrons à votre disposition. Vous les jugerez sur des aspects qualitatifs (par exemple, agréable, réaliste, etc.).

6. Quels sont les possibles risques et inconvénients si je participe ?

Vous allez voir et écouter un ensemble de stimuli de passages d'avion depuis des espaces publics. Ces stimuli sont calibrés de manière à restituer le niveau sonore réel, de fait le niveau sonore le plus élevé auquel vous pourrez être exposé sera celui d'un passage d'avion. Dans des contextes plus calmes (comme la salle où cette expérience aura lieu) vous pourrez percevoir les sons comme étant plus forts qu'ils ne le sont en réalité. Mais soyez assurés que les niveaux et les durées définis demeurent bien en dessous du seuil de ce qui peut être considéré comme potentiellement dangereux. De plus, l'outil de réalité virtuelle peut dans certaines conditions précises provoquer des haut-le-cœur. Cela a lieu lorsque vous êtes plongés dans l'environnement immersif, et qu'une simulation de mouvement est produite alors que votre corps ne suit pas ce mouvement. Mais soyez rassuré, dans le cadre de ce test, à aucun moment un mouvement n'est simulé, seul votre mouvement de tête est restitué.

Deuxièmement, le risque d'exposition au COVID-19 n'est pas nul. Tous les moyens d'hygiène et sécurité sont cependant mis en œuvre pour limiter au maximum ce risque.

Pour ces raisons, nous vous donnerons toutes les protections utiles :

- Un masque chirurgical conformément à la norme EN14683:2019;

- Une charlotte à usage unique ;
 - Une protection à usage unique du casque de réalité virtuelle ;
- Enfin, le casque de réalité virtuelle est complètement désinfecté avant votre arrivée et après chaque expérience.

Toutefois, si pour une quelconque raison, vous vous sentez mal à l'aise pendant l'expérience, veuillez en informer l'expérimentateur de manière à ce qu'il prenne les mesures nécessaires pour suspendre ou arrêter la session.

7. Quels sont les possibles avantages de ma participation ?

Si vous terminez la session d'écoute, une gratification de 30 € vous sera offerte en gage de remerciement et défraiement de vos frais de transport. Votre participation vous permettra de connaître la qualité de votre audition. Elle nous aidera certainement à mieux comprendre comment l'être humain perçoit son environnement audio-visuel.

8. Ma participation à ce projet sera-t-elle confidentielle ?

Toutes les informations que nous collectons sur vous au cours de cette recherche resteront strictement confidentielles. Vous ne pourrez pas être identifié dans les rapports et publications ultérieurs. Les seules informations personnelles qu'éventuellement nous collectons, sont : la qualité de votre audition, votre genre, votre âge, votre sensibilité au bruit, votre qualité de vie, ainsi que votre code postal.

9. Qu'advient-il des résultats du projet de recherche ?

Les résultats de cette étude seront présentés dans des conférences internationales et publiés dans des revues. Ils pourraient être également discutés occasionnellement dans des groupes de travail entre membres du projet de recherche ANIMA. Tous les documents publiés seront mis à disposition en accès libre sur la plateforme de partage sécurisée des membres du projet. Les résultats seront toujours présentés de manière groupée et anonymisée, de sorte que la confidentialité soit toujours assurée et que vous ne puissiez jamais être identifié en tant que participant. Après la fin du projet, l'ensemble des données, **exceptées** les données personnelles sur la qualité de votre audition, le genre, l'âge, la sensibilité, la qualité de vie, et la localisation du domicile, sera mis à la disposition de tout chercheur intéressé par le domaine.

10. Avis de confidentialité sur la protection des données locales :

Le délégué à la protection des données de CY Cergy Paris Université qui supervise la protection des données à caractère personnel pour notre expérimentation en France est Madame Fanny Béréhouc. Si vous êtes préoccupé par le traitement de vos données personnelles, ou si vous

souhaitez nous contacter au sujet de vos droits, veuillez la contacter à l'adresse suivante : dpo@cyu.fr

Les catégories de données personnelles utilisées seront les suivantes :

- Audiogramme (uniquement à des fins descriptives et de manière groupée - par exemple le pourcentage de personnes ayant une audition limitée lors de la communication des résultats généraux)
- Âge (uniquement à des fins descriptives et de manière groupée - par exemple la valeur moyenne lors de la communication des résultats généraux)
- Genre (uniquement à des fins descriptives et de manière groupée - par exemple les ratios de genre lors de la communication des résultats généraux)
- Code postal (de cette donnée est déduite la distance de chacun des sujets à l'aéroport le plus proche et est ensuite uniquement utilisée à des fins descriptives et de manière groupée)
- Sensibilité au bruit (uniquement à des fins descriptives et de manière groupée - par exemple les ratios de sensibilité au bruit lors de la communication des résultats généraux)
- Qualité de vie (QoL) (uniquement à des fins descriptives et de manière groupée - par exemple les ratios de QoL lors de la communication des résultats généraux)

Vos données personnelles seront traitées aussi longtemps qu'elles seront nécessaires au projet de recherche (4 ans).

11. Qui organise et finance la recherche ?

Ce projet est financé par l'Union Européenne dans le cadre du programme Horizon 2020 en Recherche et Innovation.

Nous vous remercions de votre participation,

Romain Dedieu et Catherine Lavandier

FORMULAIRE DE CONSENTEMENT A LA RECHERCHE

Veillez remplir ce formulaire après avoir lu la fiche d'information du participant et / ou écouté une explication sur la recherche.

Titre de l'étude : *Etude d'une nouvelle méthode de sensibilisation des riverains aux bruits d'avion : la réalité virtuelle*

Laboratoire ETIS, UMR 8051,
CY Cergy Paris Université, ENSEA, CNRS

Noms et informations de contact des chercheurs :

- Romain Dedieu (romain.dedieu1@cyu.fr)
- Catherine Lavandier (catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr)

Nom et information de contact du chercheur principal :

Catherine Lavandier (catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr)

Tel: 01 34 25 68 39

Merci de participer à cette recherche. L'expérimentateur doit vous expliquer le projet avant que vous acceptiez de participer. Si vous avez des questions découlant de la fiche d'information ou sur les explications qui vous ont déjà été fournies, veuillez les poser au chercheur avant de décider de prendre part. Vous recevrez une copie de ce formulaire de consentement à conserver et à consulter à tout moment.

J'ai été informé(e) verbalement et par écrit de l'étude et de la procédure expérimentale. J'ai complètement lu et compris toutes les informations. Si j'avais des questions sur cette étude envisagée, l'expérimentateur y a répondu de manière complète et satisfaisante.

Je m'engage à participer à l'ensemble du test. Si pour une raison ou pour une autre, j'arrête de participer à l'expérimentation en cours, bien que je sois conscient de la difficulté qui en découlerait pour l'ensemble de la recherche, j'accepte de ne pas recevoir la gratification.

Cergy Pontoise, le

Signature du participant

Signature de l'expérimentateur

DROIT A L'IMAGE

Je soussigné(e) (Nom, prénom)

Autorise - N'autorise pas (barrer la mention inutile)

L'expérimentateur ou Catherine Lavandier, son encadrante,

à me photographier ou à me filmer

et

à publier - exposer - diffuser

la (les) photographies ou le (les) films, me représentant pour les usages suivants :

Publication dans le manuscrit de thèse qui sera rendu publique

Publication dans des revues scientifiques spécialisées

Présentation en congrès scientifique

La ou les photographies ne seront ni vendues, ni utilisées à d'autres usages que ceux mentionnés ci-dessus.

La publication ou la diffusion de mon image, ainsi que les légendes ou commentaires accompagnant cette publication ne devront pas porter atteinte à ma dignité, à ma vie privée ou à ma réputation.

Conformément à la loi, le libre accès aux données me concernant est garanti.

Je pourrai donc à tout moment vérifier l'usage qui en est fait et je dispose du droit de retrait de cette ou ces photos/films si je le juge utile. Pour cela je pourrai contacter catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr

Cette autorisation est valable sans limitation dans le temps, sauf demande expresse de ma part.

Cergy Pontoise, le

Signature du participant

Signature de l'expérimentateur

Information document – In situ experiment

FICHE D'INFORMATION DU PARTICIPANT

IL VOUS SERA FOURNI UNE COPIE DE CETTE FICHE D'INFORMATION

Titre de l'Étude : *Etude de la perception des riverains aux bruits des survols des avions à l'aide d'un outil de réalité virtuelle.*

Laboratoire ETIS, UMR 8051,
CY Cergy Paris Université, ENSEA, CNRS

Noms et informations de contact des chercheurs :

- Romain Dedieu (romain.dedieu1@cyu.fr)
- Catherine Lavandier (catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr)

Nom et information de contact du chercheur principal :

Catherine Lavandier (catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr)

Tel: 01 34 25 68 39

12. Paragraphe d'invitation

Vous êtes invité à prendre part à un projet de recherche conduit par les membres du laboratoire ETIS dans le cadre du projet européen ANIMA (Aircraft Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches). Avant que vous ne commenciez votre participation à cette expérience, il est important que vous compreniez pourquoi ces travaux sont menés et ce que votre participation implique. **Cette étude est sans risque pour vous, car elle implique seulement une discussion entre vous et des chercheurs et une expérience de réalité virtuelle de passages d'avions.** Votre participation est totalement volontaire. Prenez le temps de lire attentivement les informations suivantes, n'hésitez pas à en discuter avec d'autres si vous le désirez. Demandez-nous si quelque chose ne vous semble pas clair ou si vous souhaitez plus d'informations. Prenez le temps de décider si oui ou non vous souhaitez prendre part à cette expérience. **Nous vous remercions de votre attention.**

13. Quel est le but de cette étude ?

Dans le cadre du projet européen ANIMA (<https://anima-project.eu>), de nouveaux outils de communication avec les riverains sont étudiés (réseaux sociaux, application mobile, réalité virtuelle). L'objectif de ce test est d'étudier si la réalité virtuelle est une bonne solution technologique pour évaluer le changement des survols des avions.

14. Pourquoi ai-je été choisi ?

Vous avez été choisi parce que vous faites partie des personnes qui ont répondu favorablement à notre campagne d'information.

15. Dois-je participer ?

La participation à cet atelier est totalement volontaire. C'est à vous de décider si vous souhaitez ou non y prendre part. Si vous décidez d'y prendre part, vous garderez cette fiche d'information avec vous, et il vous sera demandé de signer un formulaire de consentement. Vous pouvez partir à tout moment sans donner de raison. Si vous décidez de vous retirer, il vous sera demandé que faire des données déjà collectées.

16. A quoi dois-je m'attendre si je participe ?

Si vous rejoignez cette étude, vous discuterez avec les chercheurs de la façon dont vous comprenez les changements de survols prévus sur Beauchamp dans le futur.

17. Quels sont les possibles risques et inconvénients si je participe ?

Vous allez voir et écouter des passages d'avion depuis des espaces publics. Ces stimuli sont calibrés de manière à restituer le niveau sonore réel, de fait le niveau sonore le plus élevé auquel vous pourrez être exposé sera celui d'un passage d'avion. Dans des contextes plus calmes (comme la salle où cette expérience aura lieu) vous pourrez percevoir les sons comme étant plus forts qu'ils ne le sont en réalité. Mais soyez assurés que les niveaux et les durées définis demeurent bien en dessous du seuil de ce qui peut être considéré comme potentiellement dangereux. De plus, l'outil de réalité virtuelle peut dans certaines conditions précises provoquer des haut-le-cœur. Cela a lieu lorsque vous êtes plongés dans l'environnement immersif, et qu'une simulation de mouvement est produite alors que votre corps ne suit pas ce mouvement. Mais soyez rassuré, dans le cadre de ce test, à aucun moment un mouvement n'est simulé, seul votre mouvement de tête est restitué.

Tous les moyens d'hygiène et sécurité sont mis en œuvre.

Pour ces raisons, il vous est demandé de porter :

- Un masque ;
- Une charlotte à usage unique ;
- Une protection à usage unique du casque de réalité virtuelle ;

Enfin, le casque de réalité virtuelle est complètement désinfecté entre chaque participant.

Toutefois, si pour une quelconque raison, vous vous sentez mal à l'aise pendant l'expérience, veuillez en informer l'expérimentateur de manière à ce qu'il prenne les mesures nécessaires pour suspendre ou arrêter la session.

18. Quels sont les possibles avantages de ma participation ?

Votre participation nous aidera certainement à mieux comprendre comment l'être humain souhaite communiquer avec l'aéroport vis-à-vis des passages d'avions.

19. Ma participation à ce projet sera-t-elle confidentielle ?

Votre nom est bien sûr gardé confidentiel. Toutes les autres informations que nous collectons sur vous au cours de cette recherche ne permettrons jamais de vous identifier dans les rapports et publications ultérieurs). Seuls les chercheurs impliqués dans ce projet pourront avoir accès au lien entre votre nom et vos données collectées. Ce lien sera détruit en 2026, après valorisation possible de ce travail.

20. Qu'advient-il des résultats du projet de recherche ?

Les résultats de cette étude seront présentés dans des conférences internationales et publiés dans des revues. Ils pourraient être également discutés occasionnellement dans des groupes de travail entre membres du projet de recherche ANIMA. Les résultats seront toujours présentés de manière groupée et anonymisée, de sorte que la confidentialité soit toujours assurée et que vous ne puissiez jamais être identifié en tant que participant (sauf accord de votre part sur la diffusion de votre image).

21. Avis de confidentialité sur la protection des données locales :

Le délégué à la protection des données de CY Cergy Paris Université qui supervise la protection des données à caractère personnel pour notre expérimentation en France est Madame Fanny Béréhouc. Si vous êtes préoccupé par le traitement de vos données, ou si vous souhaitez nous contacter au sujet de vos droits, veuillez la contacter à l'adresse suivante : dpo@u-cergy.fr

Le lien entre votre nom et les données anonymisées sera gardé par l'expérimentateur jusqu'à la fin du projet en décembre 2021 + 5 ans pour la valorisation de la recherche.

22. Qui organise et finance la recherche ?

Ce projet est financé par l'Union Européenne dans le cadre du programme Horizon 2020 en Recherche et Innovation.

Nous vous remercions de votre participation,
Romain Dedieu et Catherine Lavandier

FORMULAIRE DE CONSENTEMENT A LA RECHERCHE

Vous avez accepté de participer à un groupe de discussion sur les changements futurs des survols d'avions sur Beauchamp, en expérimentant ces changements grâce à l'utilisation d'un outil de réalité virtuelle.

Cet atelier se déroule dans le cadre du projet de recherche ANIMA

Titre de l'Étude : Aircraft Noise Impact Management through Novel Approaches

Cette étude est menée par le laboratoire ETIS de CY Cergy Paris Université

Noms et informations de contact de l'expérimentateur :

- Romain Dedieu (<mailto:brian.katz@sorbonne-universite.fr>)
(fromain.dedieu1@cyu.fr)

Nom et information de contact du chercheur principal :

- Catherine Lavandier
Téléphone : 01 34 25 68 39
<mailto:brian.katz@sorbonne-universite.fr>
catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr

Merci de participer à cette recherche. L'expérimentateur. Si vous avez des questions découlant de la fiche d'information ou sur les explications qui vous ont déjà été fournies, n'hésitez pas à les poser au chercheur avant de prendre part à cet atelier. Vous recevrez une copie de ce formulaire de consentement à conserver et à consulter à tout moment.

J'ai été informé(e) verbalement et par écrit de l'étude et de la procédure expérimentale. J'ai complètement lu et compris toutes les informations. Si j'avais des questions sur cette étude envisagée, l'expérimentateur y a répondu de manière complète et satisfaisante.

Je m'engage à participer à l'ensemble de l'expérimentation. Je peux à tout moment arrêter de participer à l'atelier, bien que je sois conscient de la difficulté qui en découlerait pour l'ensemble de la recherche.

Beauchamp, le

Signature du participant

DROIT A LA DIFFUSION DE L'IMAGE

Je soussigné(e) (Nom, prénom)

Autorise - N'autorise pas (barrer la mention inutile)

L'expérimentateur ou toute personne impliquée dans le projet ANIMA (sous la responsabilité de Catherine Lavandier)

à me photographier

et

à publier - exposer - diffuser

la (les) photographies, me représentant pour les usages suivants :

- Publication dans des revues scientifiques spécialisées
- Présentation en congrès scientifique
- Communications autour du projet européen ANIMA (sites web par exemple)

La ou les photographies ne seront ni vendues, ni utilisées à d'autres usages que ceux mentionnés ci-dessus.

La publication ou la diffusion de mon image, ainsi que les légendes ou commentaires accompagnant cette publication ne devront pas porter atteinte à ma dignité, à ma vie privée ou à ma réputation.

Conformément à la loi, le libre accès aux données me concernant est garanti.

Je pourrai donc à tout moment vérifier l'usage qui en est fait et je dispose du droit de retrait de cette ou ces photos si je le juge utile. Pour cela je pourrai contacter

<mailto:catherine.lavandier@cyu.fr>

Cette autorisation est valable sans limitation dans le temps, sauf demande expresse de ma part.

A Beauchamp, le

Signature du participant

Signature de l'expérimentateur

